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Aircraft Mass Properties (Weight - Inertia - CG) Databank

Author: Atakan Kırkar

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15. Abstract <p>This special publication provides a somewhat detailed review of fundamental concepts in weight engineering, which are weight, inertia, and CG. The essential concepts are redefined, discussed, and grouped for ease of reference. The compiled mass properties database includes 23 distinct aircraft classes and one spacecraft category, with the corresponding references for each entry also made available. The nondimensional radii of gyration are also computed and given for each aircraft class, with the statement of subclass and configuration either in terms of geometric property or loading. The information presented herein is most useful for conceptual design studies in terms of mass properties estimation of aircraft.</p>	
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Foreword

This report represents the comprehensive compilation of aircraft mass properties of many classes and subclasses. The information presented herein is most useful for the determination of aircraft weight fractions, component weight estimations, moments and products of inertia estimations, and positioning the center of gravity during conceptual and preliminary design studies. The purpose of this report is to create a comprehensive database representing a broad spectrum of aircraft classes. The references upon which the report is built are exclusively supplied for further information and data on the topic.

This report, prepared between June and August 2025, received positive feedback from both a distinguished scholar in the field and a former president of a leading authority on mass properties. The author wishes to thank them for the time and effort they devoted to reviewing this report.

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List of Symbols

Latin	Description
b	Wing span
\bar{c}	Mean aerodynamic chord
e	Average of b and L, i.e., $e = (b+L)/2$
E	Used instead of powers of 10
g	Gravitational acceleration
I	Inertia tensor
I_{xx}, I_{yy}, I_{zz}	Mass moment of inertia about body x, y, and z axes
I_{xy}, I_{xz}, I_{yz}	Product of inertia relative to body xy, xz, and yz-axes
L	Overall length of the aircraft
m	Mass
M	Moment
n	Load factor
$\bar{R}_x, \bar{R}_y, \bar{R}_z$	Nondimensional radii of gyration about roll, pitch, and yaw axes
T	Thrust
V	Speed
W	Weight
X_{CG}, Y_{CG}, Z_{CG}	Positions of CG wrt a reference datum
Greek	Description
α	Angle of attack, defined between x_s and x_b , positive rotates x_s to x_b
ϵ	Angle between x_p and x_b , positive rotates x_p to x_b
ζ	Damping
η	Angle between x_s and x_p , positive rotates x_s to x_p
λ	Eigenvalue
τ	Time constant
ω	Frequency (natural frequency: ω_n)
Math	Description
$\forall; \triangleq; $	For all; Defined as; Absolute value
\square	Tombstone, used for QED (quod erat demonstrandum)

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
3D	Three-dimensional
A/C	Aircraft
AIAA	American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics
BDGW	Basic design gross weight
BizJet	Business jet
BL	Butt line
BWB	Blended wing body
CAD	Computer aided design
CAS	Close air support
CATIA	Computer-aided three-dimensional interactive application
CG	Center of gravity
CM	Center of mass
Config.	Configuration
FS	Fuselage station
GA	General aviation; Ground attack
HARV	High Alpha Research Vehicle (F/A-18)
HPA	Human-powered aircraft
HS	Horizontal station
HTVC	Horizontal tail volume coefficient
HWB	Hybrid wing body
KCAS	Knots calibrated airspeed
KEAS	Knots equivalent airspeed
LASRE	Linear Aerospike SR-71 Experiment
LEMAC	Leading edge (position) of mean aerodynamic chord, wrt a reference
LG	Landing gear (NLG: nose landing gear; MLG: main landing gear)
LM-5	Apollo 11 lunar module Eagle
LSA	Light sport aircraft
MAC	Mean aerodynamic chord
MIL	Military
MoI	Moment of inertia

Abbreviation	Description
MTOW	Maximum take-off weight
N/A	Not available
N/S	Not stated
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NTE	Not to exceed
OML	Outer mold line
PA	Power approach
PoI	Product of inertia
Prin.	Principal (axes)
R&D	Research & development
Recon.	Reconnaissance
Ref.	Reference
S/C	Spacecraft
SAWE	Society of Allied Weight Engineers
SI	Système international d'unités
SST	Supersonic transport
Stab.	Stability (axes)
STOVL	Short take-off and vertical landing
TVC	Thrust vectoring control
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
US/U.S.	United States
USAF	United States Air Force
UT	Utility
VS	Vertical station
VT	Vertical tail
VTOL	Vertical take-off and landing
W&B	Weight and balance
WL	Water line
wrt	With respect to
WS	Wing station
X-Plane	Experimental or research aircraft of the U.S.

List of Aircraft

Aircraft	Description	Class
F-94A	Lockheed F-94A Starfighter	Fighter
YF-86D	North American YF-86D Sabre	Fighter prototype
F-100A	North American F-100A Super Sabre	Fighter
F-104A	Lockheed F-104A Starfighter	Fighter
F-105B	Republic F-105B Thunderchief	Fighter
F-4C	McDonnell Douglas F-4C Phantom II	Fighter
F-5F	Northrop F-5F Tiger II	Fighter
F-14A	Grumman F-14A Tomcat	Fighter
F-15B	McDonnell Douglas F-15B Eagle	Fighter
F-16	General Dynamics F-16 Fighting Falcon	Fighter
F-18B	McDonnell Douglas F/A-18B Hornet	Fighter
HARV	High Alpha Research Vehicle (F/A-18)	Fighter
X-35B	Lockheed Martin X-35B	Fighter prototype
A-4D	Douglas A-4D Skyhawk	Attack
A7-A	LTV A-7A Corsair II	Attack
S-211	Aermacchi S-211	Trainer
T-38	Northrop T-38 Talon	Trainer
T-37A	Cessna T-37A Tweet	Trainer
NT-33A	Lockheed NT-33A	Trainer
JetStar	Lockheed JetStar	Business jet
C620	Cessna 620	Business jet
LJ24	Learjet 24	Business jet
LJ25D	Learjet 25D	Business jet
Tu-144	Tupolev Tu-144	Supersonic airliner
Dove Mk. 5	De Havilland Dove Mk. 5	Regional airliner
Beech 99	Beechcraft Model 99	Regional airliner
XC-142	LTV XC-142	Tiltwing VTOL
VZ-2	Vertol VZ-2	Tiltwing VTOL
VE-7	Vought VE-7 Bluebird	Biplane
PT-1	Consolidated PT-1 Trusty	Biplane

Aircraft	Description	Class
NY-1	Consolidated NY-1	Biplane
NB-1	Boeing NB-1	Biplane
XN2Y-1	Consolidated XN2Y-1	Biplane
F4B-1	Boeing F4B-1	Biplane
PW-9	Boeing PW-9	Biplane
O2U-3	Vought O2U-3 Corsair	Biplane
O-11	Curtiss O-11 Falcon	Biplane
O3U-1	Vought O3U-1 Corsair	Biplane
M2-F1	NASA M2-F1	Lifting body
M2-F2	Northrop M2-F2	Lifting body
HL-10	Northrop HL-10	Lifting body
HL-20	NASA HL-20 Personnel Launch System	Lifting body
SR-71	Lockheed SR-71 Blackbird	Reconnaissance
ASK 21	Schleicher ASK 21	Sailplane
Nimbus 2A	Schempp-Hirth Nimbus 2A	Sailplane
LK-10A	Laister-Kauffman LK-10A	Sailplane
SGS 1-36	Schweizer SGS 1-36 Sprite	Sailplane
Std. Cirrus	Schempp-Hirth Standard Cirrus	Sailplane
L-23	LET L-23 Super Blaník	Sailplane
OV-1	Grumman OV-1 Mohawk	Observation
XV-5A	Ryan XV-5A Vertifan	Jet VTOL
YAV-8B	McDonnell Douglas YAV-8B Harrier II	Jet VTOL prototype
Do 31	Dornier Do 31	Jet VTOL
XV-15	Bell XV-15	Tiltrotor VTOL
Condor	MacCready Gossamer Condor	Human-powered A/C
Albatross II	MacCready Gossamer Albatross II	Human-powered A/C
Light Eagle	MIT Light Eagle	Human-powered A/C
OV-102	Space Shuttle Columbia	Spacecraft
OV-101	Space Shuttle Enterprise	Spacecraft
LM-5	Grumman Lunar Module Eagle	Spacecraft
ATR 72	Avions de Transport Régional ATR 72	Airliner

Aircraft	Description	Class
DC-8	Douglas DC-8	Airliner
CV-880M	Convair 880M	Airliner
B367-80	Boeing 367-80	Airliner prototype
B720	Boeing 720	Airliner
B747	Boeing 747	Airliner
B-26	Martin B-26 Marauder	Bomber
B-58	Convair B-58 Hustler	Bomber
F-111C	General Dynamics F-111C	Fighter/Bomber
B1-B	Rockwell B1-B Lancer	Bomber
XB-70	North American XB-70 Valkyrie	Bomber
C-47	Douglas C-47 Skytrain	Cargo
C5-A	Lockheed C-5A Galaxy	Cargo
CN-235	CASA/IPTN CN-235	Cargo
DHC-5	De Havilland Canada DHC-5 Buffalo	Cargo
DHC-6	De Havilland Canada DHC-6 Twin Otter	Cargo
AC-130E	Lockheed AC-130E Spectre	Gunship
Navion	Ryan Navion	GA
C182	Cessna 182 Skylane	GA
C172N	Cessna 172N Skyhawk 100	GA
DHC-2	De Havilland Canada DHC-2 Beaver	GA
PA-28RT	Piper PA-28RT-201 Arrow IV	GA
C310	Cessna 310	GA
PA-30	Piper PA-30 Twin Comanche	GA
P2006T	Tecnam P2006T	GA
X-1	Bell X-1	X-plane
X-2	Bell X-2	X-plane
X-3	Douglas X-3 Stiletto	X-plane
X-15	North American X-15	X-plane
X-24A	Martin Marietta X-24A	X-plane
X-24B	Martin Marietta X-24B	X-plane
X-29	Grumman X-29	X-plane

Aircraft	Description	Class
X-31	Rockwell-MBB X-31	X-plane
X-43A	NASA X-43A	X-plane
F-16XL	General Dynamics F-16XL	Delta-wing
XF-92A	Convair XF-92A	Delta-wing
YF-102	Convair YF-102 Delta Dagger	Delta-wing
F-106B	Convair F-106B Delta Dart	Delta-wing
FD2	Fairey Delta 2	Delta-wing
BAC 221	British Aircraft Corporation 221	Delta-wing
HP.115	Handley Page HP.115	Delta-wing
Avro 707B	Avro 707B	Delta-wing
RB-49A	Northrop RB-49A	Flying wing
D-558-II	Douglas D-558-II Skyrocket	Rocket Plane

Introduction

The initial sizing of any aircraft design process starts with the takeoff weight estimation, upon which other requirements are estimated. In order to have an aircraft proposal that meets the requirements, a substantial amount of time is spent on the weight build-up. Hence, the designers need to collect a huge amount of existing aircraft data to help themselves through the process, regardless of the class of the aircraft in question. The better estimates of the mass properties will yield a superior flight performance and flight mechanics analyses at the end of the conceptual design. Hence, the design will be more credible at the beginning of the preliminary design, where the project becomes less likely to be delayed and canceled.

With those in mind, this special publication redefines, discusses, and exemplifies the mass properties in five main body sections, which are listed in the following order:

- Introduction to Weight, Inertia, and CG
- Methods for Weight Estimation
- Methods for Inertia Estimation
- Methods for CG Estimation
- Mass Properties Databank

with detailed subsections and references to the main sources of information on the topic. The first four sections constitute the essential information, while the fifth one is the presentation of mass properties of distinct aircraft classes rendered and compiled by the author. The main body of the report incorporates only the necessary equations to digest the topic. The interested reader is referred to the relevant references, where the subject is examined in depth, and more data tables and equations are explicitly provided.

Much of the effort in preparing this report was concentrated on providing a clear, concise, and step-by-step approach to estimating the mass properties. Throughout the report, the phrases “the author” or “this author” refer to the one who wrote this report. Other authors are referred to by name.

The discussion of “mass or weight” and some useful relations that are used in the inertia transformations are addressed in the Appendices, where the derivation of those equations is also covered. Appendices end with a small glossary on the weight terminology.

The purpose of this report is not to rescind textbook methodologies, but to guide their practical application in a cohesive framework. Given that tabular representations facilitate learning by enabling data comparison and structural organization, this report incorporates numerous data tables to enhance clarity and comprehension.

1 Introduction to Weight, Inertia, and CG

1.1 Several Aspects of Mass and Inertia

The preliminary estimations of weight (actually mass, see Appendix A), inertia, and center of gravity (CG) will affect the dynamic stability of the aircraft once the flight mechanics analyses are completed at the end of the conceptual design. Hence, caution needs to be taken for greater accuracy, even at the conceptual level. To better understand and exemplify the notional differences between the mass and inertia, Table 1.1 is prepared.

Table 1.1: Several Aspects of Mass and Inertia

Aspect	Mass	Inertia
Measures	Resistance to linear acceleration	Resistance to angular acceleration
Applies to	Linear motion	Rotational motion
Symbol	m (or W; see Appendix A)	I (I_{xx} , I_{xz} , etc.)
Unit	kg, lb (lb_m), or slug	$kg \cdot m^2$, $lb \cdot ft^2$, $lb \cdot in^2$, or $slug \cdot ft^2$
Depends on	Total amount of matter contained in a 3D body	Mass and how it is distributed around an axis or plane
Scalar or tensor	Scalar (1 number only)	Tensor (3 by 3 matrix for 3D bodies)
Affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translational dynamics • Dynamic modes (See App. B) • Weight & CM/CG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rotational dynamics • Dynamic modes (See App. B) • Coupling between axes (PoI)
Estimated from	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical analogy • Statistical methods • CAD (measured) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical analogy • Statistical methods • CAD (measured)
Types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empty mass (weight) • Useful mass (weight) • Fuel mass (weight) • MTOM (MTOW), etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass moments of inertia (MoI) $\Rightarrow I_{xx}, I_{yy}, I_{zz}$ • Products of inertia (PoI) $\Rightarrow I_{xy}, I_{xz}, I_{yz}$
Axes dependent	No; a fixed, scalar value	Yes (body, stability, or principal)
CG dependent	No, absolutely not	Yes; dependent on CG location

1.2 The Inertia Tensor

By convention, the mass moments and products of inertia of an aircraft are represented in a tensor form written in the body axes as follows:

$$\mathbf{I} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx} & -I_{xy} & -I_{xz} \\ -I_{xy} & I_{yy} & -I_{yz} \\ -I_{xz} & -I_{yz} & I_{zz} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \int (y^2 + z^2) dm & -\int xy dm & -\int xz dm \\ -\int xy dm & \int (x^2 + z^2) dm & -\int yz dm \\ -\int xz dm & -\int yz dm & \int (x^2 + y^2) dm \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.2.1)$$

The mass moments of inertia (diagonal elements of \mathbf{I}) are a measure of resistance to rotational motion and are always positive. On the other hand, products of inertia (off-diagonal elements of \mathbf{I}) are a measure of symmetry and can individually be zero for a symmetry plane of the aircraft. For every 3D rigid body, there exists a set of principal axes for which the PoI are all zero and the MoI are at maximum, which corresponds to the formal definition of the principal axes of the aircraft, and for which the inertia tensor takes the form:

$$\mathbf{I}_p \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx_p} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_{yy_p} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I_{zz_p} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.2.2)$$

Since the tensors are axes dependent, the inertia tensor of an aircraft can also be written in the stability axes as follows:

$$\mathbf{I}_s \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx_s} & -I_{xy_s} & -I_{xz_s} \\ -I_{xy_s} & I_{yy_s} & -I_{yz_s} \\ -I_{xz_s} & -I_{yz_s} & I_{zz_s} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.2.3)$$

The inertia tensor and its properties are discussed in what follows.

- i. For 3D bodies, the inertia tensor is a 3 by 3 square matrix, i.e., $\mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3}$.
- ii. The inertia tensor is a symmetric matrix: $\mathbf{I}_{ij} = \mathbf{I}_{ji}$, and hence $\mathbf{I} = \mathbf{I}^T$.
- iii. The inertia tensor is a positive definite matrix: a) the diagonal elements of \mathbf{I} are positive, b) the largest element of \mathbf{I} lies along the diagonal, c) $\det(\mathbf{I}) > 0$, d) $\lambda_i > 0$, for $i = \{1,2,3\}$, e) $\forall \mathbf{v} \neq 0, \mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{I} \mathbf{v} > 0$, where \mathbf{v} is an eigenvector.
- iv. The eigenvalues of the inertia tensor correspond to principal moments of inertia, i.e., $\text{eig}(\mathbf{I}) = \text{eig}(\mathbf{I}_s) = \text{eig}(\mathbf{I}_p) = \{I_{xx_p}, I_{yy_p}, I_{zz_p}\}$.
- v. The summation of MoI elements remains constant regardless of the axes wrt which they are calculated, i.e., $(I_{xx} + I_{yy} + I_{zz}) = (I_{xx_p} + I_{yy_p} + I_{zz_p}) = (I_{xx_s} + I_{yy_s} + I_{zz_s})$.

From iv., it is understood that for a given body axes MoI and PoI, the principal axes MoI can be calculated by taking the determinant of the inertia matrix written in the body-fixed axes. Usually, the inertial properties are given in any of the body, stability, or principal axes. At the trim instant, the trim α is known, hence the inertia can be transformed from body to stability axes without any difficulty. Transforming the inertia between principal and stability axes requires additional information about the angle η . But since $\eta = \alpha - \epsilon$, angle ϵ is also required. Example 1 shows how to attain those with minimum information.

The MoI and PoI represent the following notions:

1. I_{xx} represents the resistance of an A/C to a rolling motion, and it is always positive. Generally, for conventional aircraft, I_{xx} is the smallest MoI. If $I_{zz} > I_{xx} > I_{yy}$, the aircraft is said to be “wing-loaded”, which is not preferred in fighter/attack aircraft, since it makes the rolling motion harder to achieve, which is a performance indicator. All sailplanes can be considered wing-loaded.
2. I_{yy} represents the resistance of an A/C to a pitching motion, and it is always positive. Generally, for conventional aircraft, it is the second largest MoI, i.e., $I_{zz} > I_{yy} > I_{xx}$, in that case, the aircraft is said to be “fuselage-loaded”. If $I_{zz} > I_{yy} \cong I_{xx}$, the aircraft is said to be “neutrally-loaded”. Most biplanes are neutrally-loaded.
3. I_{zz} represents the resistance of an A/C to a yawing motion, and it is always positive. Generally, and for all practical purposes, it is the largest MoI, which makes the yawing motion harder than the pitching and rolling motions.
4. I_{xy} represents the coupling between rolling and pitching motions, sometimes also referred to as “oblique-wing inertial effect”, and yawing motion is unaffected by the coupling. It is zero for an aircraft that has an xz-plane of symmetry, positive if the oblique wing has a positive skew angle, i.e., right wing forward; and either positive or negative for an aircraft that has asymmetric mass distribution on the xy-plane.
5. I_{xz} represents the coupling between rolling and yawing motions, sometimes also referred to as “nose-high/nose-low effect”, and pitching motion is unaffected by the coupling. It is zero for an aircraft whenever x_p and x_b are coincident, i.e., mass is equally distributed above and below of the x_b -axis and front and aft of the z_b -axis, which is hard to achieve. Almost all conventional aircraft have a nonzero value of I_{xz} .
6. I_{yz} represents the coupling between pitching and yawing motions, sometimes also referred to as “wing-high/wing-low effect”, and rolling motion is unaffected by the coupling. It can be of negligible value if the y_b -axis runs through the mid-mounted wings. If the wings are high- or low-mounted, it will still be of negligible value for most aircraft. Generally, $|I_{xz}| > |I_{xy}| > |I_{yz}|$, for conventional aircraft, and $I_{xy} = I_{yz} = 0$, for linear flight mechanics models for practical purposes.

1.2.1 Inclination of the Principal Axis

The inclination of the principal axis with respect to body axes (usually 1 to 4 degrees for conventional aircraft, see Section 5 for examples) is governed by the following equation [1]:

$$\tan 2\epsilon = \frac{2I_{xz}}{I_{zz} - I_{xx}} \quad (1.2.4)$$

and remember that $\alpha = \eta + \epsilon$. The inclination of the principal axes with respect to stability axes is governed by the following equation:

$$\tan 2\eta = \frac{2I_{xz_s}}{I_{xx_s} - I_{zz_s}} \quad (1.2.5)$$

Say, in a trimmed flight, where α and body axes moments and product of inertia are known, Equation 1.2.4 can be solved to attain ϵ . Once epsilon is obtained, the body axes inertia can be converted to stability axes inertia with the help of Appendix C, and unknown η can be either solved from Equation 1.2.5 or from $\eta = \alpha - \epsilon$, if needed.

Example 1: For a computer-simulated light fighter jet, the CAD measured body axes MoI and PoI are given at 25.5% MAC as follows:

$$\mathbf{I} = \begin{bmatrix} 6000 & 0 & -1131 \\ 0 & 35000 & 0 \\ -1131 & 0 & 38400 \end{bmatrix} \text{ slug-ft}^2 \quad (1.2.6)$$

It is also known that at the trim instant $\alpha = 2.3$ deg. For this aircraft, calculate:

- a. Principal axes MoI and angle ϵ
- b. Stability axes MoI, PoI, and angle η

State the methods used. Any further comments are encouraged.

Solution to Example 1:

Part a of the problem can be solved by three methods as follows.

a.1. Method of Determinant

Since the inertia tensor is given in the body axes, the determinant of the I matrix will yield the principal axes MoI. Taking the determinant of matrix I, one attains: $I_{xx_p} = 5960.57$, $I_{yy_p} = 35000.00$, and $I_{zz_p} = 38439.43$, all in slug-ft².

The angle ϵ is found by Equation 1.2.4 as $\epsilon = 1.9968 \approx 2$ deg.

a.2. Method of Thelander

In order to apply the method of Thelander, the angle ϵ must first be determined. This is already done in part a.1., and it is known that $\epsilon = 1.9968 \approx 2$ deg. Using Table C.4, one can obtain the MoI in the principal axes as follows: $I_{xx_p} = 5960.57$, $I_{yy_p} = 35000.00$, and $I_{zz_p} = 38439.43$, all in slug-ft².

a.3. Method of Wolowicz

In order to apply the method of Wolowicz, the angle ϵ must first be determined. This is already done in part a.1., and it is known that $\epsilon = 1.9968 \approx 2$ deg. Using Table C.10, one can obtain the MoI in the principal axes as follows: $I_{xx_p} = 5960.57$, $I_{yy_p} = 35000.00$, and $I_{zz_p} = 38439.43$, all in slug-ft².

Discussion: If the inertia tensor is given in the body axes and principal axes MoI are sought, it is easier to apply the method of determinant since it reduces the risk of computational errors substantially. On the other hand, the methods of Thelander and Wolowicz estimate the principal axes MoI identically.

Part b of the problem can either be solved by the method of Wolowicz or Thelander. For completeness, both methods are applied and compared.

b.1. Method of Thelander

In order to apply the method of Thelander, the angle η must first be determined. This is done by $\eta = \alpha - \epsilon \Rightarrow \eta = 0.3$ deg. Using Table C.2, one can obtain the MoI and PoI in the stability axes as follows: $I_{xx_s} = 5961.48$, $I_{yy_s} = 35000.00$, $I_{zz_s} = 38438.52$, and $I_{xz_s} = -171.87$, all in slug-ft².

b.2. Method of Wolowicz

In order to apply the method of Wolowicz, the angle η must first be determined. This is done by $\eta = \alpha - \epsilon \Rightarrow \eta = 0.3$ deg. Using Table C.8, one can obtain the MoI and PoI in the stability axes as follows: $I_{xx_s} = 5961.48$, $I_{yy_s} = 35000.00$, $I_{zz_s} = 38438.52$, and $I_{xz_s} = -171.87$, all in slug-ft².

Discussion: Now it is apparent that both methods give the same results for any transformation of inertia between the axes. One further check can be done as follows: if Equations 1.2.4 and 1.2.5 are solved for angles and summed, one obtains:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{2} \arctan \left(\frac{2I_{xz}}{I_{zz} - I_{xx}} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \arctan \left(\frac{2I_{xz_s}}{I_{xx_s} - I_{zz_s}} \right) \quad (1.2.7)$$

Plugging the numbers obtained by the two methods, which are essentially the same, into Equation 1.2.7, it can be shown that $\alpha = 2.30$ deg, which was given by the problem statement.

1.3 Center of Gravity

1.3.1 Introduction

The center of gravity (CG) is one of the most important parameters in aircraft design, whose allowable range has a direct effect on aerodynamics, landing gear position, tail size & position, flight performance, stability, and control of the aircraft. Physically, it is more accurate to refer to the point of moment balance as the “center of mass”; however, in practice, the term “center of gravity” has been conventionally adopted in aerospace and weight engineering. This discussion is briefly covered in Appendix A.

Traditionally, the components of CG can be expressed by one or a combination of the following alternatives as given in Table 1.2:

Table 1.2: Alternative Ways of Expressing CG

Alter. CG	Most Common (In Analysis)	Technical Drawings	Least Common
x-component	X_{CG} , wrt ref. datum or % MAC	FS	HS
y-component	Y_{CG} , wrt ref. datum	BL	WS
z-component	Z_{CG} , wrt ref. datum	WL	VS

Selecting a reference datum and measuring the components of CG wrt that point is the most common approach for CG positioning. This can either be done at a conceptual level as discussed in Section 4.1, or one can define a fixed point in CAD, and may measure the components of the CG wrt that point. Practically, though, it is more convenient to express the X_{CG} in terms of % MAC. However, since Y_{CG} and Z_{CG} cannot be expressed as a percent of MAC, the following definitions are adopted to pinpoint the Y_{CG} and Z_{CG} in technical drawings: BL and WL, which correspond to butt line and water line and are given in length units wrt a fixed point. Using a fixed point as a reference, one can locate the three CG components of an aircraft in space using FS, BL, and WL. Usually, this fixed point is positioned beneath the aircraft’s nose at the symmetry plane, and aligned with the line formed by a tangent that passes along the bottom surface of the landing gears or the lower surface of the fuselage, and shown as (0.0, 0.0, 0.0). In practice, the published technical reports often omit Y_{CG} and Z_{CG} for data protection purposes, and prevent overshare of data. As a result, X_{CG} is typically the only publicly available CG component.

Usually, the allowable CG range is as critical as a specific CG location. Many aircraft classes have distinct allowable CG ranges. The CG range for fighter/attack aircraft, on the other hand, is typically as long as the long side of an A4 paper, and most of the time this corresponds to about 8 to 10% of the MAC. See Figs. 1.1-1.3, for other examples.

1.3.2 Implications of X_{CG}

X_{CG} is primarily related to longitudinal stability and controllability. Placing the CG too far forward will usually have the opposite effect to that of putting it too far aft. Hence, these implications can be compared as in Table 1.3, mostly in terms of flight performance. The table can also be read as an overview of how aircraft performance, maneuverability, and stability are affected when the CG shifts forward or aft during flight.

Table 1.3: Implications of X_{CG} on Several Aspects of Aircraft

Aspect	Forward X_{CG}	Aft X_{CG}
Takeoff/Landing runway	Longer	Shorter
Longitudinal stability	Increased	Decreased
Controllability	Less (insufficient HT authority)	More (sufficient HT authority)
Maneuverability	Less pitch maneuverability	More pitch maneuverability
Loads on wheel	Decreased MLG load	Decreased NLG load
Taxi	Easier	Harder
Tipback & Nose-up tendency	Safer	More prone
Trim AoA/drag	Increased	Decreased
Fuel burn during cruise	More fuel	Less fuel
L/D	Decreased	Increased
Stall speed	Increased	Decreased
Cruise speed	Reduced (for a given T & W)	Increased (for a given T & W)
Takeoff/Landing speed	Higher	Lower
Maximum ceiling	Lowered	Increased
Range/Endurance	Reduced	Increased
Spin entry	Safer	More prone
Rate of climb	Reduced	Increased

1.3.3 Implications of Y_{CG}

Y_{CG} is primarily related to lateral stability and controllability. Ideally, an aircraft should have near-zero Y_{CG} for all practical purposes, i.e., trimming and analyzing without lateral thrust offset. However, even in aircraft that appear symmetrical, small asymmetries on the order of a few millimeters or centimeters (depending on A/C) can occur and still be tolerated, due to structural variations, fixed equipment placement, payload distribution, or fuel imbalances during burn. Other than that, lateral CG asymmetry can also occur in transport aircraft due to passenger movement and placement.

Generally speaking, the resultant lateral CG offset, to either side, is still small and can easily be compensated with the application of asymmetric thrust, if available, or with the joint deflection of ailerons and rudders.

Practically, lateral CG offset limits should be established as soon as possible to assure that the aileron deflection will suffice in all phases of flight where such phenomena might occur, mostly due to fuel burn and payload drop. The lateral-directional stability of the aircraft will be slightly degraded for a small lateral CG offset, and the aircraft will probably perform steady heading sideslip (flight with a nonzero β) where it normally would cruise (zero β).

1.3.4 Implications of Z_{CG}

Z_{CG} is primarily related to directional stability and controllability. However, its effect on longitudinal and lateral stability should not be overlooked. Aircraft are generally designed so that the Z_{CG} lies close to the thrust line and within a narrow vertical envelope. The implications of Z_{CG} being either above or below the thrust line are given in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4: Implications of Z_{CG} on Several Aspects of Aircraft

Aspect	Z_{CG} Above Thrust Line	Z_{CG} Below Thrust Line
Nose-up/down	Nose-down moment when T \uparrow	Nose-up moment when T \uparrow
Roll stability	Less roll stability	More roll stability
Dutch-roll stability	Less Dutch-roll stability	More Dutch-roll stability
Spiral stability	Less spiral stability	More spiral stability
Yaw-roll coupling	More prone to adverse roll in yaw or sideslip	Less yaw-roll coupling, yaw is more isolated from roll
Ground stability	More tip-over or nose-over tendency on ground	More stable on the ground (especially in taildraggers)

1.3.5 CG Envelope

Generally speaking, five envelopes will be of importance as the transition from conceptual to preliminary design (or preliminary to detail design) is approved for any aircraft, and these are conventionally fixed and named as given in Table 1.5.

Table 1.5: Five Most Critical Envelopes in Aircraft Design

Name	Depicts & Shows	Examples
CG envelope	X-axis is CG in % MAC or FS, y-axis is weight. It is mostly for X_{CG} , but Y_{CG} and Z_{CG} will also be needed later on. It shows the allowable CG range for design.	Fig. 1.1-1.3
CG travel	It depicts how the CG travels as the fuel is burned & payload is dropped, and also known as the “potato curve”. It also ideally shows the aerodynamic center.	[2, p. 449] [3, p. 618] [4, p. 230]
V-n diagram	It shows the speed limits vs design limit and ultimate load factors.	[5, p. 31-45]
Flight envelope	Altitude vs Mach/KEAS/KCAS envelope for level flight.	[6, p. 670]
X-plot	Also known as scissor-plot; CG range on x-axis in terms of % MAC and HT size (S_{ht}/S_w) or HTVC in y-axis.	[7, p. 167]

Figure 1.1: Typical CG Envelope for General Aviation - Light Utility

Figure 1.2: Typical CG Envelope for Military Transport - Cargo Plane

Figure 1.3: Typical CG Envelope for Short-Haul Airliner - Commuter Aircraft

The reader must have noticed that all the top left lines of the typical CG envelope diagrams are oblique. The reason for this phenomenon is left as a brainstorming exercise. Most of the envelope examples can be found in the owner's manuals of homebuilt aircraft (e.g., Rutan Long-EZ) and flight manuals of complex, professionally engineered aircraft (e.g., F-16).

2 Methods for Weight Estimation

Introduction

Weight engineering is a critical discipline in aircraft design. But as with most of the disciplines in aircraft design, it is not done just for weights, as aerodynamics is not just for aerodynamics. All disciplines that can be encountered during the design of an aircraft contribute to achieving a safe, controllable, certifiable design. No certification authority will ever permit the designed aircraft to be flown just because it performs the best aerodynamics or can do what others, i.e., competitors, cannot do with the same size and weight. The final objective is always to have an aircraft that does what it is supposed to do, as required, being controllable at all times, requiring minimum pilot work, and complying with the certification requirements. Ironically, the estimated design gross weight will always be lower than it actually weighs once produced. Then comes, as a first aid, the famous ballast to compensate for the shifted CG location, which was once promised to the flight mechanics and control engineers. However, since the aircraft now weighs more, the performance engineers are not content with the range and endurance. It is all a big trade-off.

Nevertheless, a reliable first estimate of the design gross weight and the estimates based on the first estimate will significantly reduce the man-hours and program costs for the development aircraft and will probably make every discipline content working on the project. Ideally, 1 to 5% underestimation of the design gross weight can, without much difficulty, be compensated later on, since the performance, flight mechanics, and control engineers would be expecting it, and be ready beforehand. However, a 5 to 15% underestimation of the design gross weight might lead to significant changes in the design, possible delays, or even cancellation of the project. The reason for such cases is quite obvious, as more weight means more lift, more lift means more drag, and more drag means more thrust, and more thrust means more money spent per second. Even if the money might impose no problems, though it always does, the “more thrust” might not be easily found. If the thrust issue can be solved, then “more drag” will be unacceptable to comply with the performance requirements. Moreover, where to put more fuel that is to be spent with more thrust, that all of a sudden we are faced with, just because the actual aircraft weighs more than the estimations?

Since the weight of the aircraft was underestimated, another problem is the CG shift to be addressed due to the additional weight: it is probably not in the allowable range now. However, all the analyses were conducted assuming that the CG would fall in that range. This would also mean that the sizing studies for horizontal and vertical tails were erroneous, since they were designed wrt the assumed CG location, which has now obviously shifted. Another issue with the CG shift is the stability concern. The aircraft may be too stable or too unstable now, which was not the intent at the beginning. All these discussions suffice to signify the importance of weight estimation, even at the conceptual design phase.

The Role of SAWE on Mass Properties

The Society of Allied Weight Engineers (SAWE), founded in 1939 and initially organized as the Society of Aeronautical Weight Engineers, is an international professional organization dedicated to the advancement of mass properties engineering across the aerospace, marine, and other transportation industries. Since its establishment, SAWE has provided a forum for the exchange of technical knowledge through conferences, technical papers, recommended practices, and training programs. Its activities support the development of standards, tools, and methodologies that enhance the accuracy and efficiency of weight engineering, while fostering collaboration among engineers, researchers, and industry professionals worldwide. SAWE should not be confused with SAE International (formerly the Society of Automotive Engineers), a global standards body for the aerospace, automotive, and commercial vehicle industries, whose scope extends broadly across engineering disciplines rather than focusing primarily on mass properties.

Through its textbooks, conference proceedings, and technical papers, SAWE has established a robust foundation for weight engineering on a global scale. The renowned textbook, which was edited by the prominent mass properties engineer Roy N. Staton (1937-2021) and titled *Introduction to Aircraft Weight Engineering* [8], has become an indispensable reference for weight and balance engineers worldwide.

Through its recommended practices, SAWE aims to establish standardized methods for reporting the mass properties of aircraft, spacecraft, missiles, and other vehicles. This report follows SAWE RP A-8 [9], the standard for aircraft weight and balance reporting, as illustrated in Table 2.5 and 4.1.

The conferences and journals of SAWE have served as significant vehicles for technical publishing, and the Society's publications have been influential in the work of prominent aerospace engineers, including Jan Roskam, Egbert Torenbeek, and Daniel P. Raymer. Some of the SAWE papers that are closely related to the content of this report include:

- SAWE Paper No. 78 by Chawla [10]: is the influential paper on MoI estimation by the method of radii of gyration.
- SAWE Paper No. 783 by Wisniewski [11]: is a conceptual design study of four different V/STOL aircraft (jet lift VTOL, tiltwing VTOL, lift fan VTOL, and turbofan STOL), which also covers the major group weight (wing, HT, VT) trends of similar aircraft.
- SAWE Paper No. 3271 by Sellner [12]: is a major report on statistical wing mass estimation of jet fighter/bomber and trainer aircraft, which also covers the European (German, Italian, French, Swedish, etc.) practice in mass breakdown presentation.

Note: The author is also a proud member of the Central European Chapter of SAWE.

Classification of Methods

The weight estimation methods can be classified according to their fidelity and applicability at each design stage. Generally, these classes can be identified for pre-conceptual, conceptual, preliminary, and detail design stages; hence, a total of four. While Roskam [5] mentions the first two because his text covers up to preliminary design, Torenbeek [7] cites all four, adding that these classifications are by no means standard. The following classes are therefore the present author's digest and do not necessarily reflect the practice of any corporation.

Class I - Pre-conceptual design method. The application of Class I weight estimations requires minimal knowledge about the aircraft, and the outer mold line may not always be available. This method is entirely based on the anticipations of the category of the aircraft that is to be designed. The parameters to be estimated during the Class I method are empty weight fraction (structures, propulsion, fixed equipment), fuel fraction, payload fraction, and takeoff gross weight using similar aircraft data required for initial "sizing". The equation that plays a role in this method is called the "unity equation" and is given in Equation 2.2.2. Thus, this method is also known as "historical analogy" as mentioned in Table 2.1. The final objective is to attain an approximate takeoff gross weight using weight fractions of similar aircraft of the same category, e.g., commercial transport, fighter, sailplane, etc. The moments and products of inertia and CG are not yet discussed at this stage. Note that Class I method is prerequisite to the other methods that follow.

Class II - Conceptual design method. The application of Class II weight estimations requires the outline of the aircraft (and a three-view drawing), general characteristics & dimensions, and performance parameters. The canopy, landing gear, control surfaces, and engine placements are done, and the configuration is ready to be estimated in terms of weight via the statistical methods given in Tables 2.3 and 2.4. Estimated group weights are tabularized in Group Weight Statement as in Table 2.5, and the x, y, and z components of CG can be determined as in Table 4.1. Considering that the aircraft will perform takeoff with nominal CG, the estimated CG at takeoff gross weight can be assumed to lie between $\pm 5\%$ MAC for X_{CG} , $\pm 0.5\%$ wing span for Y_{CG} , and $\pm 3\%$ MAC for Z_{CG} . Flight mechanics analyses may be initiated once a low-fidelity aerodynamic database (e.g., from handbook methods or linear flow solvers) is available. At this stage, the MoI and PoI are to be estimated via the methods described in Sections 3.1 to 3.3. At the end of this stage of the weight calculations, the expected accuracy is about 70-90%, and the "growth factor" may be discussed.

Note: Weight and balance engineers preferably play a key role during Class I and II weight estimations, depending on the type of A/C, e.g., fighter jet, mini UAV, etc., configuration, e.g., usual or unusual, and the available manpower of the corporation. The Weight Control Plan (WCL), contingency, and uncertainty analysis, on the other hand, may be required at proposal submittal or at a specified time following contract award, if applicable.

Class III - Preliminary design method. As the aircraft design proceeds through the preliminary design stage, the number of design inputs increases, and the major weight groups are divided into subgroups, necessitating professional weight management. At this stage of the weight estimations, feedback from hydraulics, electronics, and propulsion teams is well appreciated, and usually, that feedback brings about additional weight to the project since now every weight group is subgrouped and well-defined. From now on, the weight estimation procedure can be assigned to weight and balance engineers who have to deal with complex systems, drawings, details, and a huge amount of data in CATIA or Siemens NX, as well as in Excel. At this stage, it is better to impose a “not to exceed”, i.e., NTE, weight limit on each major group based on loads and structural analysis. Even at this stage of the weight estimations, statistical methods cannot be completely abandoned. At the end of this stage of the weight calculations, the expected accuracy is about 85-95%.

Class IV - Detail design method. At this stage of the weight calculations, the weight and balance engineers take the whole responsibility to communicate with subsystems and reflect each design detail into their databook and CAD. Some produced and purchased subsystems come along with their known weights, which eases the bookkeeping of some subgroups. At that stage, it is expected that the calculated weight and inertia have no more than ± 1 to 5% deviations wrt the actual values.

Note: Weight and balance engineers need to play a significant role during Class III and IV weight calculations. Even though the layout is being designed by the configuration designer, the tasks of weight, CG, and inertia calculations are assigned to W&B engineers.

The applicability of all classes is summarized in Figure 2.1 in terms of the weight estimation flowchart, which concludes with the weight measurement.

Figure 2.1: Weight Estimation Flowchart

The detailed group weight statement that is established on the weight measurement of the production aircraft is the actual “manufacturer data” which reflects the final report on weight.

2.1 Methods Applicable at Conceptual Design

At the most basic level, aircraft component group weight fractions or individual component weight estimations can be carried out with the methods presented in Table 2.1, which also correspond to one or two of the classes introduced before.

Table 2.1: Component Weight Estimation Methods

Method	Covered in	Design Stage
Historical analogy [†]	See Table 2.2.	Conceptual
Statistical	See Tables 2.3 and 2.4.	Conceptual Preliminary
CAD	Industrial approach: every component is drawn in detail with real material specifications to attain accurate weights.	Conceptual Preliminary Detail

Note. †: Estimate empty weight (structures, propulsion, equipment) fraction using historical data.

It is to be noted that the application of all methods (historical analogy, statistical, CAD) is possible at the conceptual design stage, depending on how far the design process is maintained. Usually, once the conceptual design is completed, it is expected that the statistical methods will be well utilized. Employing CAD this early in the process might be viewed as an overuse of resources and man-hours. One can match the newly mentioned methods with the Class definitions of previous discussions as follows:

Historical analogy: Estimate weight fractions (empty, fuel, and payload weight fractions) that sum up to unity equation (Equation 2.2.2). The objective is to establish a meaningful BDGW and MTOW during pre-conceptual design that leads to conceptual design. It is considered a Class I method.

Statistical: Estimate component weights using statistical equations given in the references of Table 2.3 that sum up to the basic design gross weight. Technology improvements are reflected in the equations by fudge factors, which can be found in [6, p. 580]. It is considered a Class II method, although it is still used in parallel with CAD for Class III weight calculations. Thus, it can be employed during conceptual and preliminary design stages.

CAD: Every component is drawn in detail, and the weight and inertia of thousands of components are accumulated. Though it is a Class IV method to be used in detail design, the process can also start at the conceptual design stage. Software commonly used at this stage includes CATIA (Dassault Systèmes), NX (Siemens), Creo (PTC), to name a few. OpenVSP (NASA) is commonly used to create the outer mold line (OML) quickly, but the detailed components are subject to further development in CATIA, etc.

2.2 The Unity Equation - Estimating Weight Fractions

The unity equation is derived from the most common weight build-up equation

$$W_0 = W_e + W_f + W_p + W_c \quad (2.2.1)$$

where W_0 is the basic design gross weight (usually basic design takeoff gross weight), W_f is the fuel weight, W_p is the payload weight, and W_c is the crew weight. Equation 2.2.1 can be written as:

$$\frac{W_e}{W_0} + \frac{W_f}{W_0} + \frac{W_p}{W_0} + \frac{W_c}{W_0} = 1 \quad (2.2.2)$$

which is known as the “unity equation”. The concept designer plays long enough, i.e., iterates, with the modified version of Equation 2.2.2 as given in Equation 2.2.3 until the aircraft in question is “sized” in terms of weights. Even though the unity equation is mostly written for BDGW, it can also be used to size the MTOW by simply replacing the subscript 0 with MTOW; this would give yet another build-up for MTOW, which should also be determined as early as possible, or maybe there is already a requirement for MTOW limit.

$$W_0 = \frac{W_p + W_c}{1 - (W_f/W_0) - (W_e/W_0)} \quad (2.2.3)$$

Notice the trade-off the designer must perform between the fractions in Equation 2.2.2, which are basically called empty weight, fuel, and payload fraction, respectively, while crew weight is known (hence W_c/W_0). This would mean that, given a fixed empty weight fraction, to satisfy the unity equation, the designer must trade off between the fuel and payload fractions.

The best and suggested method for estimating the empty weight fraction is to generate a trend using the existing aircraft class, for which the designed aircraft exhibits similarities and falls under the same category. The fuel fraction, on the other hand, will appear immediately if the payload fraction is known beforehand, meaning that the designed aircraft has a specific requirement for the payload. If not, the fuel fraction will be estimated by the mission profile, and how much fuel is needed to complete one mission, with some fuel to spare upon landing. All these concerns are still to be followed from *magna opera* of Raymer and Gudmundsson.

Furthermore, Roskam [5, p. 3-15] provides a step-by-step solution to the initial weight build-up equation with three applied examples of twin-engine propeller-driven airplane, jet transport, and fighter aircraft. The designers need to have a huge amount of data in order to come up with meaningful fractions for the aircraft class under consideration. To guide them, Table 2.2 is prepared, which serves as guidance as to where to find those fractions for many aircraft classes before the application of the unity equation.

Table 2.2: Empty Weight and Other Weight Fractions Info Available in Literature

Aircraft Class	Given Info	Ref.
LSA, Sailplane, Agricultural, etc.	Empty weight, useful weight, and fuel weight fractions for LSA and statistical empty weight relations for several GA aircraft	[13, p. 139-141]
Many	Empty weight fraction trends curve	[6, 14, p. 30]
Many	Empty weight fraction as a function of takeoff weight ($W_e/W_0 = AW_0^C$)	[6, 14, p. 31]
Many	Empty weight fraction as a function of takeoff weight ($W_e/W_0 = aW_0 + b$)	[15, p. 111]
Fighter	Structures, propulsion, auxiliaries, avionics, and weapon weight fractions of some fighter aircraft	[16, p. 10]
Many	Empty weight fractions for fighter, bizjet, transport, etc., aircraft are given in tabular form	[15, p. 110]
Many	Typical empennage and landing gear mass fraction ranges are given for various A/C classes	[17, p. 353-354]
Commercial Transport	Typical average structure, propulsion, fixed equipment, and empty weight fractions are given for passenger transport, freighters, and bizjets	[18, p. 266]
Many	Statistical empty weight equations based on A, T/W, W/S, maximum speed, and takeoff gross weight for various aircraft	[6, p. 148-149]
Many	MTOW, landing, empty, and payload weight information for many aircraft classes	[19, p. 186-194]
Many	Countless weight fractions and manufacturer component weight data rendered by Roskam	[5, p. all]
GA & Commercial Transport	Many aircraft component weight fractions are given in ranges as well as empty weight fraction	[4, p. 235-237]
Airliner, Cargo, Bomber	Fuel fractions at takeoff for various cruise-dominant aircraft are given	[3, p. 155]
Homebuilt	Group weight statement of some homebuilt A/C	[20, p. 136]
Transport	W_e estimation eq. for subsonic transport A/C	[21, p. 18]
Satellite	Numerous satellite weight fractions	[22, 23]

2.3 Statistical Component Weight Estimation Method

The statistical component weight estimation methods are collectively given in Table 2.3. These methods are to be used until the detail design phase.

Table 2.3: Sources of Information for Statistical Weight Estimation

Ref.	Author/Publisher	Applicable to
[2]	I. Kroo & R. Shevell - Desktop Aeronautics	Commercial Transport (Airliner, BizJet, Cargo)
[3]	L. M. Nicolai - AIAA	Fighter / Attack, Transport, Light Utility
[4]	A. K. Kundu - Cambridge	Civil Aircraft (Airliner, BizJet)
[5]	J. Roskam - DARcorp	GA, Commercial Transport, Military Patrol / Bomber / Transport, Fighter / Attack
[18]	E. Torenbeek - TU Delft	GA, Commercial Transport
[24]	R. Staton - Vought Aeronautics	Fighter / Attack
[25]	R. Staton - Vought Aeronautics	Cargo / Transport
[26]	A. C. Jackson - Aero Commander/Rockwell	GA / Light Utility
[27]	D. P. Wells et al. - NASA	Transport, Fighter/Attack, GA, HWB
[28]	L. R. Jenkinson et al. - Butterworth-Heinemann	Commercial Transport
[29]	W. Stender - OSTIV	Sailplane
[30]	P. Morelli - OSTIV	Sailplane
[31]	J. Gundlach - AIAA	UAV
[32]	G. J. Harloff & B. M. Berkowitz - NASA	Hypersonic
[33]	Martin Marietta Corp.	Spacecraft
[22]	C. Cuerno-Rejado et al. - J. Aerosp. Eng.	Satellite
[23]	P. N. Pathak - Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.	Satellite
[34]	J. B. Nowell Jr. - NPS	Missile

Note. Refs. [24–26] are also collectively presented in Raymer [6].

The component weight estimations carried out by the methods presented in Table 2.3 shall then be presented in a classical group weight statement as in Table 2.5 per SAWE RP A-8.

The aircraft that is being designed may not always fall into the classes given in Table 2.3. In that case, one of the classes must be chosen to initiate the component weight analysis. Table 2.4 is prepared as guidance for such a case.

Table 2.4: Suggested Methods of Component Weight Estimation for Some A/C Classes

Aircraft Class	Use the Methods Available for	Ref.
Fighter / Attack	Fighter / Attack	[3, 5, 24, 27]
Military Trainer		
Low speed	General Aviation	[3, 5, 18, 26, 27]
High speed	Fighter / Attack	[3, 5, 24, 27]
BizJet		
Airliner	Commercial Transport	[2, 4, 5, 18, 28]
Supersonic Airliner [†]		
Regional Turboprops		
Below 12500 lb	General Aviation	[3, 5, 18, 26, 27]
Above 12500 lb	Commercial Transport	[2, 4, 5, 18, 28]
Patrol		
Bomber	Military Patrol / Bomber / Transport	[5]
Cargo		
Homebuilt & LSA		
Agricultural	General Aviation / Light Utility	[5, 18, 26, 27]
Biplane & Bush plane		
BWB & HWB	HWB	[27]
Sailplane	Sailplane	[29, 30]
UAV [‡]	UAV or General Aviation / Light Utility	[5, 18, 26, 27, 31]
Hypersonic	Hypersonic	[32]
Spacecraft [*]	Spacecraft	[33]
Satellite [*]	Satellite	[22, 23]
Missile [*]	Missile	[34]

Note. †: Use fighter / attack aircraft air induction weight estimation for supersonic airliner inlet.

‡: ForUCAV, use either military patrol / bomber / transport or fighter / attack depending on configuration.

*: Not aircraft, taken here for completeness.

Even at the conceptual design level of an aircraft, in order to examine the weight budget, the classical group weight statement table is generated as shown in Table 2.5.

Table 2.5: Typical Group Weight Statement for Fighter/Attack Aircraft

A/C Name	Item W (lb or kg)
Structures Group	
Wing	
Horizontal Tail	
Vertical Tail	
Fuselage	
Main Landing Gear	
Nose Landing Gear	
Engine Mounts	
Firewall	
Engine Section	
Air Induction	
Propulsion Group	
Engines	
Tailpipe	
Engine cooling	
Oil cooling	
Engine Controls	
Starter	
Fuel system	
Equipment Group	
Flight Controls	
Instruments	
Hydraulics	
Electrical	
Avionics	
Furnishings	
Air conditioning	
Handling gear	
Misc. empty weight	
Total Empty Weight	
Useful Load Group	
Crew	
Fuel	
Oil	
Cargo	
Passengers	
Misc. useful load	
Design Gross Weight	

The group weight statement provides a valuable reference for monitoring weight status and comparing it with future estimations. For different aircraft classes, additional subgroups may be introduced. For a variety of aircraft group weight statements, see Refs. [5] and [18].

3 Methods for Inertia Estimation

3.1 Radii of Gyration Method for MoI

At the conceptual design level, the mass moments of inertia calculation process using the radii of gyration method is shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Workflow Diagram for Estimating the Mass Moments of Inertia

In order to apply the method, first, the outer mold line of the full-scale and sized aircraft must be available. Second, overall aircraft length, L , and wing span, b , must be noted. Shall the designed aircraft fall under a known category, i.e., fighter, military cargo, airliner, etc., Section 5 must be referred to for the average radii of gyration of that category. Then, initial MoI estimations can be carried out either using Equation 3.1.1 or 3.1.2. This method offers the most rapid estimation of the moment of inertia (MoI) for a given aircraft class, at the cost of reduced accuracy.

The mass moments of inertia are either computed in SI or US customary units.

In SI units (results in $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$):

$$I_{xx} = \frac{b^2 m \bar{R}_x^2}{4} \quad I_{yy} = \frac{L^2 m \bar{R}_y^2}{4} \quad I_{zz} = \frac{e^2 m \bar{R}_z^2}{4} \quad (3.1.1)$$

In US units (results in $\text{slug}\cdot\text{ft}^2$):

$$I_{xx} = \frac{b^2 W \bar{R}_x^2}{4g} \quad I_{yy} = \frac{L^2 W \bar{R}_y^2}{4g} \quad I_{zz} = \frac{e^2 W \bar{R}_z^2}{4g} \quad (3.1.2)$$

where $e = (b+L)/2$ and $g = 32.174 \text{ ft/s}^2$. Note that these estimations will yield the moments of inertia in body axes if the nondimensional radii of gyration are given for the body axes' MoI. This means that both MoI and the radii of gyration are axis-dependent.

Unless the design is truly unusual, because otherwise CAD is the only way to obtain MoI and PoI, the aircraft usually falls into a category of already existing real designs, and a meaningful radii of gyration can be chosen from Section 5 to estimate the MoI, for initial assessments. Note that this method cannot be applied to the estimation of I_{xz} . Since PoI is the representation of how symmetric the mass is distributed. The radii of gyration method for MoI estimation can be considered a Class I method.

3.2 Statistical Curve Fit Method for MoI

If, for the aircraft under consideration, a similar group of existing aircraft data can be found, then the moment of inertia estimation can be carried out by means of the statistical curve fit method. This method is superior to the radii of gyration method since similar existing aircraft MoI data are fitted by creating a trend line. This method can be applied both with simple linear regression (dependent variable: W) and multiple linear regression (dependent variables: W , b , L) analysis.

The following example details the use of statistical curve fit methods applied for MoI estimation.

Example 2: For a conceptual twin jet, twin VT fighter aircraft, calculated empty, BDGW, and MTOW are 34000, 42000, and 50000 lb, respectively. For this aircraft, generate

- simple linear curve fit, based on W
- linear curve fit, based on W and e^2

to be used in further stability and control analyses. Estimate and list the MoI results for empty, BDGW, and MTOW.

Comment on your results. Compare two methods. Given: $e = 60$ ft.

Solution to Example 2: Using Table 5.3 and selecting F-14, F-15B, and F/A-18 as candidates for the databank, Figures 3.2 and 3.3 are generated in accordance with parts a and b of the problem.

Figure 3.2: Solution to Part a of Example 2

Figure 3.3: Solution to Part b of Example 2

The estimations for the MoI for empty, BDGW, and MTOW, using both methods, are given in the following listing:

- 34000 lb (Empty), $I_{zz} = 157418.1$ (linear fit), and 178092.0 slug-ft² (relation fit)
- 42000 lb (BDGW), $I_{zz} = 211353.3$ (linear fit), and 219996.0 slug-ft² (relation fit)
- 50000 lb (MTOW), $I_{zz} = 265288.5$ (linear fit), and 261900.0 slug-ft² (relation fit)

This author suggests the use of a linear fit relation for the estimation of moment of inertia at the early conceptual design phase, especially if its R^2 value is significantly higher than that of the relation fit equation. Also note that the statistical curve fit method can be considered a Class II method.

3.3 Statistical Curve Fit Method for PoI

The application of the statistical curve fit method for PoI is similar to that of MoI. Usually, the estimated PoI value will be in low fidelity. However, a significant enhancement to this method is possible with a large amount of similar aircraft PoI data, especially in the early conceptual design phase, i.e., when the concept drawing is not yet available, or a quick flight mechanics analysis is sought with minimum information. The proper use of this method with much data would yield PoI estimations within 10% accuracy of the actual value once measured for specific loadings. Better methods exist for both MoI and PoI estimations: these require systematic calculation and a detailed drawing and are rather called “calculations”.

3.4 Component Build-Up Method for MoI and PoI

A superior method to radii of gyration (Class I) and statistical curve fit (Class II) methods is the component build-up method for MoI and PoI estimations, better put, calculations. Before applying this method, Class II weight estimation and CG analysis must be finalized.

The mathematical foundation of this method follows from Equation 1.2.1 with a slight modification, i.e., introduction of the individual CG positions of major components, as given through Equations 3.4.1 to 3.4.6.

$$I_{xx} = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \{(y_i - y_{cg})^2 + (z_i - z_{cg})^2\} \quad (3.4.1)$$

$$I_{yy} = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \{(z_i - z_{cg})^2 + (x_i - x_{cg})^2\} \quad (3.4.2)$$

$$I_{zz} = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \{(x_i - x_{cg})^2 + (y_i - y_{cg})^2\} \quad (3.4.3)$$

$$I_{xy} = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i (x_i - x_{cg})(y_i - y_{cg}) \quad (3.4.4)$$

$$I_{yz} = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i (y_i - y_{cg})(z_i - z_{cg}) \quad (3.4.5)$$

$$I_{xz} = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i (x_i - x_{cg})(z_i - z_{cg}) \quad (3.4.6)$$

Upon pinpointing or estimating the CG positions of major components, as in Table 4.1, this method is applicable for better MoI and PoI estimations.

The choice of the reference datum for X_{CG} , Y_{CG} , and Z_{CG} is at the discretion of the engineer, as covered in Section 1.3. This method also applies to non-detailed CAD models (otherwise, use the calculation as output by CAD), with the positioning of the major components available. It also assumes that the number of major components is sufficiently high and their own MoI and PoI about their own CG become negligible. Otherwise, the Equations 3.4.1 to 3.4.6 take $\sum_{i=1}^n I_{jk}$ as addition to the right-hand side, where $j, k = \{x, y, z\}$. (See [5, p. 121-122]).

The component build-up method for MoI and PoI estimation can be considered a Class III method. The Class IV method would be the computation of MoI and PoI via CAD.

4 Methods for CG Estimation

4.1 The Method of Moments

The method of moments, or moment balance, is the only practical way to estimate or compute the CG location at conceptual, preliminary, and detail design stages. Moreover, the CAD software uses it to position the CG of the vehicle, too. The estimation of the CG of the aircraft can be performed as soon as the component weight estimations are completed, using the methods in Table 2.3 or 2.4. Then, all the calculated component weights are arranged in a tabular form as in Table 4.1 with longitudinal moment arms to calculate individual moments with respect to a reference datum, which could be at the nose of the fuselage, any point along the fuselage, or at some arbitrary point along a line above or below of the x-axis. If the first is used as a reference datum, then all the moment arms become positive. The final objective is to estimate the position of X_{CG} wrt the chosen reference datum. Then, for any practical reason, it can be written in terms of % MAC by using Equation 4.1.2.

Table 4.1: CG Estimation via Group Weight Statement

Group	Weight	Arm	Mom	Group	Weight	Arm	Mom
Structures	W_{str}	-	M_{str}	Equipment	W_{eq}	-	M_{eq}
Wing				Flight Controls			
Horizontal Tail				Instruments			
Vertical Tail				Hydraulics			
Ventral Tail				Electrical			
Fuselage				Avionics			
Main Landing Gear				Furnishings			
Nose Landing Gear				Air conditioning			
Engine Mounts				Handling gear			
Firewall				% Weight Allowance		-	-
Engine Section				Empty Weight Allow.	W_{alw}		
Air Induction				Empty Weight	W_e		
Propulsion	W_{prop}	-	M_{prop}	Useful Load	W_{use}	-	M_{use}
Engines				Crew			
Tailpipe				Fuel			
Engine cooling				Oil			
Oil cooling				Cargo			
Engine Controls				Passengers			
Starter				Misc. Useful Load			
Fuel system				BDGW	W	X_{CG}	M

Table 4.1 is prepared in accordance with Table 2.5, regarding a generic fighter/attack aircraft group weight statement. A similar tabular form can be prepared for any class of aircraft by introducing additional subgroups that may arise or eliminating absent subgroups. In Table 4.1, empty weight and BDGW are established as follows: $W_e = W_{str} + W_{prop} + W_{eq} + W_{alw}$ and BDGW is the sum of the empty weight and useful load weight, i.e., $W = W_e + W_{use}$. Also, $W_{alw} = (W_{str} + W_{prop} + W_{eq}) \times (\% \text{ Weight Allowance})/100$. It is worth noting that the X_{CG} values for W_e and BDGW are likely to be different points.

On the other hand, $M = M_{str} + M_{prop} + M_{eq} + M_{use}$. Thus, for Table 4.1, the X_{CG} is determined as: $X_{CG} = M/W$, where M and W are just defined, more specifically:

$$X_{CG} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n M_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i x_{cg_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i} \quad (4.1.1)$$

with respect to a reference datum, about which the moment arms are measured. The calculation is similar for Y_{CG} and Z_{CG} . The estimated X_{CG} location will be in terms of distance (length unit) measured from the reference datum. For practical purposes, X_{CG} can be written in terms of % MAC using Equation 4.1.2.

$$X_{CG \text{ in } \% \text{ MAC}} = \left(\frac{X_{CG} - X_{LEMAC}}{\bar{c}} \right) \times 100 \quad (4.1.2)$$

where X_{CG} and X_{LEMAC} should be measured wrt the same reference datum used. If it is assumed that the mass of the components will be equally distributed along the y-axis, then Y_{CG} can be taken as zero. On the other hand, a similar table analysis can be performed for the calculation of Z_{CG} , or it can be assumed to lie approximately along the centerline of the fuselage, which is typically close to the x-body axis. The essential mass, inertia, and CG properties of an A/C (overall called “mass properties”) in order to conduct flight mechanics analyses are given in Table 4.2 with their properties briefly summarized.

Table 4.2: Essential Mass Properties of an Aircraft for Flight Mechanics Analyses

Symbol	Property
W	Gross weight of the aircraft at the time of analysis
X_{CG}, Y_{CG}, Z_{CG}	CG positions wrt reference datum, in length units
I_{xx}, I_{yy}, I_{zz}	MoI about CG wrt reference axes, usually wrt the body axes; transformation to another axes is covered in Appendix C
I_{xy}, I_{xz}, I_{yz}	PoI about CG wrt reference axes, usually wrt the body axes; transformation to another axes is covered in Appendix C

5 Mass Properties Databank

This section compiles weight, inertia, CG, and basic geometric data (b and L) for a variety of aircraft classes. The geometric data and mass properties are used to compute the nondimensional radii of gyration. In the following subsections, a total of 104 aircraft data sets (including a few S/C) are compiled, all of which are real and flown designs except for HL-20 (not flown). The order of appearance of aircraft classes does not follow a deliberate pattern.

5.1 Jet Fighter

5.1.1 Generations 1st to 3rd

Table 5.1: Mass Properties Data of Jet Fighter Generations 1st to 3rd

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
F-94A	13614	N/S	11029	26543	36801	-660	26.1	37.30	44.49	[35]
YF-86D	14285	Body	7340	26200	23380	320	N/A	37.05	40.26	[36]
F-100A	23989	Body	10976	57100	64975	942	N/A	36.50	46.42	[37]
F-104A	16300	Prin.	3549	58611	59669	2.76°	7.0	21.94	54.66	[38]
F-105B	35370	Prin.	10300	140000	181000	0.0	30.8	34.90	64.33	[39]
F-4C	38924	Body	25001	122186	139759	2177	28.9	38.67	58.27	[38]
F-5F	12950	Body	4640	54500	57700	13.0	16.0	26.66	47.33	[40]

Table 5.2: Radii of Gyration for Jet Fighter Generations 1st to 3rd

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
F-94A	Fighter	Single Engine	Single VT	0.2737	0.3560	0.4561
YF-86D		Single Engine	Single VT	0.2195	0.3816	0.3755
F-100A		Single Engine	Single VT	0.2102	0.3770	0.4503
F-104A		Single Engine	T-Tail	0.2413	0.3936	0.5667
F-105B		Single Engine	Single VT	0.1754	0.3508	0.5172
F-4C		Twin Engine	Single VT	0.2351	0.3449	0.4435
F-5F		Twin Engine	Single VT	0.2547	0.4917	0.6473
Average values for Jet Fighter Generations 1 st to 3 rd →				0.2300	0.3851	0.4938

The delta-wing fighters are covered in Table 5.45, which are indeed interceptors. Notably, the average values for American tailless delta-wing interceptors align closely with those of earlier fighters, despite their distinct configuration, as given in Table 5.46.

5.1.2 Generations 4th to 5th

Table 5.3: Mass Properties Data of Jet Fighter Generations 4th to 5th

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
F-14A	52000	Body	51509	232773	275627	2654	16.2	64.14	62.67	[41]
F-15B	35900	Body	25480	166620	186930	-1000	26.1	42.83	63.78	[35,42]
F-15B	37426	Body	30345	198687	223214	-5070	26.3	42.83	63.78	[43]
F-16	20500	Body	9496	55814	63100	982	35.0	30.00	49.40	[44]
F-18B	32167	Body	16179	119353	131500	-2120	22.7	37.42	56.00	[45]
HARV	36099	Body	22789	176809	191744	-2305	23.8	37.40	56.00	[46]
X-35B	30979	Body	16581	92035	102594	-1688	N/A	33.00	51.18	[47]
	34428		17916	100365	112109	-2023				

Table 5.4: Radii of Gyration for Jet Fighter Generations 4th to 5th

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
F-14A	Fighter	Twin Engine	Twin VT	0.1760	0.3830	0.4119
F-15B		Twin Engine	Twin VT	0.2231	0.3832	0.4856
				0.2385	0.4098	0.5197
F-16		Single Engine	Single VT	0.2574	0.3789	0.5013
F-18B		Twin Engine	Twin VT	0.2150	0.3902	0.4911
HARV		Twin Engine	Twin VT	0.2409	0.4483	0.5597
X-35B [†]		Single Engine	Empty	0.2515	0.3821	0.4905
			Nominal	0.2480	0.3785	0.4864
Average values for Jet Fighter Generations 4 th to 5 th →				0.2313	0.3943	0.4933

Note. †: Use the radii of gyration for X-35B to estimate the MoI of a conceptual 5th-generation fighter jet. This aircraft is also taken to the X-plane category in Section 5.21.

Evaluation of Tables 5.2 and 5.4 demonstrates that the mean nondimensional radii of gyration exhibit minimal variation between earlier and modern fighter aircraft, indicating that their inertial characteristics, relative to geometry, remain remarkably consistent across generations.

Note: The piston-propeller-driven fighter aircraft data of the World War II era are to be found in Roskam [5] and Garcia [48]. That data can be used for the initial inertia estimation of turboprop-powered military trainers such as Hürkuş (Türkiye), Pilatus PC-9 (Switzerland), and Grob G 120TP (Germany).

5.2 Attack

Table 5.5: Mass Properties Data of Attack Aircraft

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
A-4D	17578	Body	8090	25900	29200	1300	25.0	27.5	39.330	[39]
A7-A	21889	Body	13635	58966	67560	2933	30.0	38.7	46.128	

Table 5.6: Radii of Gyration for Attack Aircraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
A-4D	Attack	Light	Nominal	0.2799	0.3501	0.4376
A7-A				0.2314	0.4037	0.4699
Average values for Light Attack A/C with one vertical tail →				0.2557	0.3769	0.4538

5.3 Jet Trainer

Table 5.7: Mass Properties Data of Jet Trainer Aircraft

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
S-211	4000	Body	800	4800	5200	200	25.0	26.30	30.540	[49]
T-38	9000	Body	1438	25874	26779	0.0	23.0	25.25	46.370	[39]
T-37A	6360	Body	7985	3326	11183	0.0	27.0	38.42	29.265	[49]
NT-33A	13700	Body	23800	21100	43800	480	26.3	37.54	37.750	[38]
	11800		12700	20700	32000	480	26.0			

Table 5.8: Radii of Gyration for Jet Trainer Aircraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
S-211	Trainer	Military	Empty	0.1929	0.4069	0.4551
T-38			Nominal	0.1796	0.4148	0.5465
T-37A			Heavy	0.3310	0.2803	0.4446
NT-33A			Nominal	0.3983	0.3729	0.5388
			PA	0.3135	0.3980	0.4963
Average values for Jet Trainers with 2 engines on fuselage →				0.2831	0.3746	0.4963

5.4 Business Jet

Table 5.9: Mass Properties Data of Business Jets

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
JetStar	38205	Body	118779	135876	243513	5061	25.0	53.75	60.40	[38]
	23904		42273	126099	160104	5470				
C620	15000	Body	64811	17300	64543	0.0	25.0	55.10	41.42	[49]
LJ24	13000	Body	28000	18800	47000	0.0	32.0	34.00	43.25	[49]
LJ25D	11000	Body	28000	22000	47000	N/A	N/A	34.10	47.58	[50]

Table 5.10: Radii of Gyration for Business Jets

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
JetStar	BizJet	Utility	Heavy	0.3721	0.3542	0.5018
		Transport	Light / PA	0.2807	0.4314	0.5144
Average values for BizJet with 4 jet engines on rear fuselage →				0.3264	0.3928	0.5081
C620	BizJet	Light Trans.	MTOW	0.4279	0.2941	0.4876
Average values for BizJet with 4 piston engines under the wings →				0.4279	0.2941	0.4876
LJ24	BizJet	Light Trans.	Heavy	0.4897	0.3154	0.5585
LJ25D	BizJet	Light Trans.	Nominal	0.5307	0.3372	0.5742
Average values for BizJet with 2 jet engines on rear fuselage →				0.5102	0.3263	0.5664

5.5 Supersonic Airliner

Table 5.11: Mass Properties Data of Supersonic Airliners

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
Tu-144	303000	Body	1206096	12985528	13993327	-201591	N/A	88.58	196.83	[51]

Table 5.12: Radii of Gyration for Supersonic Airliners

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
Tu-144	Airliner	Supersonic	Double-Delta	0.2555	0.3773	0.5402
Average values for Tu-144 SST (also use for Concorde) →				0.2555	0.3773	0.5402

5.6 Regional Airliner

Table 5.13: Mass Properties Data of Regional Airliners

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
Dove Mk. 5	7912	Body	10672	12833	21519	N/A	N/A	57.00	39.24	[52]
	9099		11341	13181	22290					
Beech 99	11000	Body	15189	20250	34141	4371	16.0	45.93	44.62	[49]
	7000		10085	15148	23046	1600				

Table 5.14: Radii of Gyration for Regional Airliners

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
Dove Mk. 5	Airliner	Regional	No Fuel	0.2311	0.3682	0.3888
			Full Fuel	0.2222	0.3480	0.3690
Average values for twin piston-propeller driven Regional Airliner →				0.2267	0.3581	0.3789
Beech 99	Airliner	Regional	MTOW	0.2902	0.3449	0.4414
			Nominal	0.2965	0.3740	0.4546
Average values for twin turboprop-driven Regional Airliner →				0.2934	0.3595	0.4480

5.7 Tiltwing VTOL

Table 5.15: Mass Properties Data of Tiltwing VTOL

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
XC-142	37474	Body	173000	122000	267000	7000	20.0	67.50	58.07	[53]
VZ-2	3432	Body	1634	2937	3988	N/A	33.5	24.88	26.41	[54]

Table 5.16: Radii of Gyration for Tiltwing VTOL

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
XC-142	VTOL	Tiltwing	Hover	0.3611	0.3525	0.4823
VZ-2	VTOL	Tiltwing	Hover	0.3146	0.3974	0.4769
Average values [†] for Tiltwing VTOL →				0.3379	0.3750	0.4796

Note. †: Can be used for the initial MoI estimation of modern tiltwing eVTOL UAV such as Dufour Aerospace Aero-200.

5.8 Biplane

Table 5.17: Mass Properties Data of Biplanes

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
VE-7	2208	Body	1478	1498	2510	-3.4°	N/A	34.11	24.45	[55]
PT-1	2512		2205	2168	3343	N/A		34.79	27.67	
NY-1	2622		2336	2530	3887	-0.15°		34.48	27.75	
NB-1	2544		2756	2306	4143	0°		36.83	25.17	
XN2Y-1	1567		818	944	1316	0°		28.00	20.75	
F4B-1	2540		1147	1590	2092	-0.25°		30.00	20.61	
F4B-2	2816		1063	1795	2378	N/A		30.00	20.34	
PW-9	2885		1400	1930	2573	-3.3°		32.08	22.85	
O2U-3	3550		2817	2880	4530	0.35°		34.50	24.63	
O-11	4558		2877	4238	6290	0.20°		38.00	28.33	
O3U-1	4057		2740	3283	5112	N/A		36.00	27.25	

Table 5.18: Radii of Gyration for Biplanes

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
VE-7	Biplane	Training	MTOW	0.2721	0.3822	0.4131
PT-1			MTOW	0.3055	0.3809	0.4191
NY-1			MTOW	0.3106	0.4016	0.4439
NB-1			Heavy	0.3206	0.4291	0.4670
XN2Y-1			Heavy	0.2927	0.4243	0.4265
Average values for Training Biplanes →				0.3003	0.4036	0.4339
F4B-1	Biplane	Fighter	MTOW	0.2541	0.4355	0.4069
F4B-2			MTOW	0.2323	0.4453	0.4142
PW-9			Heavy	0.2463	0.4061	0.3901
Average values for Fighter Biplanes →				0.2442	0.4290	0.4037
O2U-3	Biplane	Observation	Light	0.2929	0.4149	0.4335
O-11			MTOW	0.2372	0.3861	0.4018
O3U-1			Heavy	0.2590	0.3745	0.4027
Average values for Observation Biplanes →				0.2630	0.3918	0.4127
Grand average values for Biplanes →				0.2748	0.4073	0.4199

Note: The average data for biplanes can be used for the initial MoI estimation of any biplane, e.g., aerobatic biplane A/C.

5.9 Lifting Body

Table 5.19: Mass Properties Data of Lifting Bodies

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
M2-F1	1182	Body	225	1100	1125	-25	N/A	14.17	22.17	[56]
M2-F2	6000	Body	956.3	5583	6005	-417	54.0	9.54	22.20	[57]
HL-10	6466	Body	1353	6413	7407	399	51.7	13.60	21.17	[38]
HL-20	19100	Body	7512	33594	35644	N/A	55.5	13.89	29.50	[58]

Table 5.20: Radii of Gyration for Lifting Bodies

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
M2-F1	Lifting Body	Tech. Demo.	Light	0.3493	0.4936	0.6091
M2-F2			BDGW	0.4747	0.4929	0.7151
HL-10			BDGW	0.3816	0.5337	0.6984
HL-20			BDGW	0.5122	0.5100	0.7143
Average values for Lifting Bodies →				0.4295	0.5076	0.6842

5.10 Reconnaissance

Table 5.21: Mass Properties Data of Reconnaissance Aircraft

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
SR-71	60728	Body	220660	954850	1172039	19200	20.1	56.7	107.4	[59]
	75349		230880	1035520	1252710	44710	27.3			
	70158		224670	992280	1209470	28390	23.3			

Table 5.22: Radii of Gyration for Reconnaissance Aircraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
SR-71	Recon.	Mach 3+	Baseline	0.3814	0.4188	0.6074
			LASRE	0.3502	0.3916	0.5638
			Test bed	0.3580	0.3972	0.5741
Average values for Mach 3+ Recon. A/C →				0.3632	0.4025	0.5818

5.11 Sailplane

Table 5.23: Mass Properties Data of Sailplanes

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
ASK 21	840	Body	6518.4	1446.1	7403.3	N/A	67.6	55.77	27.395	[60]
Nimbus 2A	994.28	Body	3319.76	510.39	3763	N/A	30.0	66.60	24.05	[61]
LK-10A	875.2	Body	578.25	435.2	1488.4	N/A	N/A	49.87	21.33	[61]
SGS 1-36	874	Body	1014.15	640.94	1632.96	49.4	33.8	46.17	20.58	[61,62]
Std. Cirrus	738.55	Body	930.8	306.83	1195.6	N/A	29.8	49.21	20.83	[61]
L-23	1124	Body	2080	1010	2700	190	N/A	53.15	27.89	[63]

Table 5.24: Radii of Gyration for Sailplanes

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
ASK 21	Sailplane	Club Class	Empty	0.5666	0.5433	0.8099
Nimbus 2A		Open Class	Nominal	0.3112	0.3380	0.4869
LK-10A		MIL Training	MTOW	0.1849	0.3750	0.4156
SGS 1-36		Club Class	MTOW	0.2647	0.4721	0.4646
Std. Cirrus		Open Class	MTOW	0.2588	0.3510	0.4122
L-23		Training	MTOW	0.2904	0.3856	0.4339
Average values for Sailplanes (5 of 6 have T-tail) →				0.3128	0.4108	0.5039

5.12 Observation

Table 5.25: Mass Properties Data of Observation Aircraft

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
OV-1	12000	Body	17700	20200	36400	1660	23→30	42.0	40.7	[64]

Table 5.26: Radii of Gyration for Observation Aircraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
OV-1	Observation	Light	Nominal	0.3280	0.3616	0.4778
Average values for twin turboprop Light Observation A/C →				0.3280	0.3616	0.4778

5.13 Jet VTOL

Table 5.27: Mass Properties Data of Jet VTOL

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
XV-5A	7541	Body	4193	14160	16311	946	FS248.4	29.83	44.517	[65]
	9200		4316	16660	18824	1172	FS241.0			
	11622		4596	19981	22030	1708	FS245.3			
YAV-8B	16280	Body	6547	30927	34685	1382	FS343.6	30.33	46.33	[66]
Do 31	45000	Body	284000	205000	447000	N/A	23.0	55.80	67.60	[67]

Table 5.28: Radii of Gyration for Jet VTOL

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
XV-5A	Jet VTOL	Experimental	Empty	0.2836	0.3492	0.4488
			BDGW	0.2605	0.3429	0.4365
			Full Fuel	0.2392	0.3341	0.4202
Average values for Experimental Jet VTOL →				0.2611	0.3421	0.4352
YAV-8B	Jet VTOL	Attack	Nominal	0.2372	0.3375	0.4320
Do 31	Jet VTOL	Cargo	Nominal	0.5107	0.3582	0.5795

5.14 Tiltrotor VTOL

Table 5.29: Mass Properties Data of Tiltrotor VTOL

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
XV-15	13000	Body	48053	17570	60532	1181	N/A	32.17	42.08	[66]
X-100	3500	Body	1300	2151	3200	N/A	N/A	16.08	28.30	[68]

Table 5.30: Radii of Gyration for Tiltrotor VTOL

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
XV-15	VTOL	Tiltrotor	BDGW	0.6780	0.3134	0.6594
X-100	VTOL	Tiltrotor	BDGW	0.4300	0.3143	0.4889
Averaging the values for Tiltrotor VTOL is not feasible due to major design differences						

5.15 Human-Powered Aircraft

Table 5.31: Mass Properties Data of Human-Powered Aircraft

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
Condor	212	Body	6731	668	1316	N/A	N/A	96.00	30.00	[69]
Albatross II	222		4303	389	815			96.00	50.50	
Light Eagle	249		2891	251	2146			114.17	28.87	[70]

Table 5.32: Radii of Gyration for Human-Powered Aircraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
Condor	HPA	-	with Pilot	0.6659	0.6712	0.4486
Albatross II				0.5202	0.2974	0.2967
Light Eagle				0.3386	0.3945	0.4657
Averaging the values for Human-Powered Aircraft is not feasible due to major design differences						

5.16 Spacecraft

Table 5.33: Mass Properties Data of Spacecraft

S/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
OV-102	198144	Body	8.95E+5	6.92E+6	7.20E+6	1.67E+5	N/A	78.06	122.25	[37]
OV-101	182986		7.59E+5	5.77E+6	5.91E+6	1.31E+5				[71]
LM-5	15572	Body	12164	12840	15347	N/A	11.868 [†]	31 [‡]	22.92 [*]	[72]

Note. †: Center of mass height above landing gear footpad, ft.

‡: Diameter, diagonally across extended landing gear

*: Legs extended height

Table 5.34: Radii of Gyration for Spacecraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
S/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
OV-102	Spacecraft	Orbiter	Nominal	0.3089	0.5483	0.6827
OV-101				0.2960	0.5211	0.6437
Average values for Space Shuttle Orbiter →				0.3025	0.5347	0.6632
LM-5	Spacecraft	Lunar Module	Nominal	0.3234	0.4494	0.4177

5.17 Airliner

Table 5.35: Mass Properties Data of Airliners

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
ATR 72	47400	Body	213800	220120	423050	N/A	N/A	88.58	89.17	[73]
DC-8	1.90E+5	Stab.	3.09E+6	2.94E+6	5.58E+6	2.8E+4	15.0	142.3	150.7	[39]
	2.30E+5		3.77E+6	3.56E+6	7.13E+6	4.5E+4				
CV-880M	1.55E+5	N/S	1.51E+6	2.51E+6	4.10E+6	0.0	25.0	120.00	129.33	[38]
	1.26E+5		1.15E+6	2.45E+6	4.07E+6	0.0	19.5			
B367-80	1.50E+5	Body	2.57E+6	2.25E+6	4.73E+6	0.16E+6	30.0	130.80	129.58	[74]
B720	1.80E+5	Body	2.28E+6	3.45E+6	5.75E+6	2°	15→31	130.83	136.16	[64]
B747	6.36E+5	Body	18.2E+6	33.1E+6	49.7E+6	0.97E+6	25.0	195.68	231.8	[38]
	5.64E+5		13.7E+6	30.5E+6	43.1E+6	0.83E+6				

Table 5.36: Radii of Gyration for Airliners

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
ATR 72	Airliner	Regional	MTOW	0.2720	0.2742	0.3813
Average values for twin turboprop Regional Airliners →				0.2720	0.2742	0.3813
DC-8	Airliner	Narrow-body	PA (LG up)	0.3215	0.2961	0.4196
			Cruise	0.3228	0.2962	0.4311
CV-880M			Nominal	0.2951	0.3530	0.4680
			PA (LG up)	0.2856	0.3868	0.5172
B367-80			Nominal	0.3590	0.3391	0.4893
B720			Nominal	0.3086	0.3648	0.4803
Average values for four jet-engined narrow-body Airliners →				0.3154	0.3393	0.4676
B747	Airliner	Wide-body	Nominal	0.3101	0.3531	0.4692
			PA (LG up)	0.2857	0.3599	0.4640
Average values for four jet-engined wide-body Airliners →				0.2979	0.3565	0.4666

The design of airliners has attracted the attention of esteemed scholars, and some textbooks have been specifically written on the topic, such as *Civil Jet Aircraft Design* by Jenkinson et al. [28] and *Synthesis of Subsonic Airplane Design* by Torenbeek [18]. **Note:** A recent study on the mass properties of the Boeing 787-8 for a hundred different possible loading configurations yielded that $I_{zz} = 0.97(I_{xx} + I_{yy})$. The corresponding authors [75] suggest that “for large commercial passenger airliners, the yaw inertia is approximately equal to the sum of the pitch and roll inertias.”

5.18 Bomber

Table 5.37: Mass Properties Data of Bombers

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
B-26	28512	Body	76000	70000	142000	N/A	16.5	65.00	58.20	[76]
B-58	1.5E+5	Stab.	3.6E+5	1.04E+6	1.2E+6	2.7E+4	33.0	56.82	96.78	[39]
			3.8E+5	1.04E+6	1.4E+6	5.1E+4	28.0			
	9.0E+4		3.4E+5	6.5E+5	9.5E+5	1.9E+4	28.0			
F-111C	69900	Body	73344	344866	411017	3977	24.5	70.00	73.50	[77]
B1-B	288000	Body	9.50E+5	6.40E+6	7.10E+6	-5.3E+4	N/A	136.7	145.6	[78]
XB-70	384546	Body	1.80E+6	19.9E+6	22.1E+6	-0.88E6	21.8	105.0	193.4	[38]
	300000		1.45E+6	16.0E+6	17.2E+6	-0.60E6	23.5			

Table 5.38: Radii of Gyration for Bombers

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
B-26	Bomber	Medium	Nominal	0.2849	0.3054	0.4110
Average values for twin piston-propeller driven Medium Bomber →				0.2849	0.3054	0.4110
B-58	Bomber	Strategic	Cruise	0.3093	0.3087	0.4178
				0.3178	0.3087	0.4513
				0.3881	0.3150	0.4799
Average values for delta-wing 4 jet-engined Bomber (Stab. Axes) →				0.3384	0.3108	0.4497
F-111C [†]	Fighter/Bomber	Supersonic	Nominal	0.1660	0.3428	0.3834
B1-B [‡]	Bomber	Supersonic	Nominal	0.1507	0.3673	0.3991
Average values for Variable-Sweep Strategic Supersonic Bomber →				0.1584	0.3551	0.3913
XB-70	Bomber	Experimental	Nominal	0.2338	0.4220	0.5764
			PA	0.2375	0.4284	0.5757
Average values for XB-70 (Delta-Wing Supersonic Bomber) →				0.2356	0.4252	0.5761

Note. †: Data is given when wings are swept to 16 degrees.

‡: Data is given when wings are swept to 65 degrees.

Note: More data on the radii of gyration for a variety of the older-generation of bombers (pre-1962) can be found in the paper of Garcia [48], which contains information on 29 aircraft. A subset of this dataset, comprising 13 aircraft, is reproduced by Roskam [5]. The aircraft mentioned in the references include both piston-propeller types (now largely obsolete) and jet-powered bombers, such as the B-45 and B-52.

5.19 Cargo Plane

Table 5.39: Mass Properties Data of Cargo Planes

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
C-47	23000	Stab.	61887	89500	139200	-4689	N/A	95.50	63.75	[53]
C5-A	654362	Body	27.8E+6	31.8E+6	56.2E+6	2.46E+6	30.0	219.2	247.83	[38]
CN-235	33290	Body	125000	97000	250000	N/A	30.0	84.68	70.05	[79]
DHC-5	40000	Body	273000	215000	447000	0.0	15.0	96.00	77.00	[80]
DHC-6	12000	Body	24300	22010	41020	0.0	15.0	65.00	47.50	
AC-130E	110000	Body	1.4E+6	9.7E+5	2.2E+6	6.1E+4	25.0	132.6	97.74	[81]

Table 5.40: Radii of Gyration for Cargo Planes

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
C-47	Cargo	MIL Trans.	Nominal	0.1949	0.3510	0.3505
Average values for low-wing twin piston-propeller Cargo Planes →				0.1949	0.3510	0.3505
C5-A	Cargo	MIL Trans.	Nominal	0.3373	0.3191	0.4502
Average values for high-wing four jet engine Cargo Planes →				0.3373	0.3191	0.4502
CN-235	Cargo	MIL Trans.	Heavy	0.2596	0.2764	0.4018
DHC-5	Cargo	UT/MIL	Nominal	0.3087	0.3416	0.4384
DHC-6	Cargo	UT/MIL	Heavy	0.2484	0.3235	0.3729
Average values for high-wing twin turboprop engine Cargo Planes →				0.2722	0.3138	0.4044
AC-130E	GA/CAS	Gunship	Nominal	0.3052	0.3411	0.4405
Average values for high-wing four turboprop engine Cargo Planes →				0.3052	0.3411	0.4405

Note: Since AC-130E is a modification to the C-130 cargo plane, it is categorized under this section, even though it operates as a gunship.

Figure 5.1: Left View of C-5A

Note. Reprinted from Heffley & Jewell [38].
The figure exemplifies the use of FS and WL to some parts of the aircraft.

5.20 General Aviation

Table 5.41: Mass Properties Data of General Aviation Aircraft

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
Navion	2750	Stab.	1048	3000	3530	0.0	29.50	33.38	27.41	[39]
C182	2650	Body	946	1346	1967	0.0	26.40	35.88	25.00	[82]
C172N	1927	Body	1029	1092	1890	91	28.80	36.09	26.90	[83]
DHC-2	5045	Body	3960	5111	8230	87	38.00	48.00	30.25	[84]
PA-28RT	2420	Body	1789	2486	3796	N/A	27.82	35.43	27.80	[85]
C310	4600	Body	8884	1939	11001	0.0	33.00	36.90	29.50	[49]
PA-30	3600	Body	2800	1900	4500	80	N/A	35.98	25.17	[86]
P2006T	2513	Body	1193	1421	2162	N/A	19.00	37.40	28.50	[87]

Table 5.42: Radii of Gyration for General Aviation Aircraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
Navion	GA	Light Utility	Nominal	0.2098	0.4323	0.4229
Average values for low-wing single piston engine GA A/C →				0.2098	0.4323	0.4229
C182	GA	Light Utility	Heavy	0.1889	0.3234	0.3211
C172N	GA	Light Utility	Nominal	0.2297	0.3175	0.3567
Average values for high-wing single piston engine GA A/C →				0.2093	0.3205	0.3389
DHC-2	GA	Floatplane	Nominal	0.2094	0.3775	0.3703
Average values for high-wing single piston engine Floatplane →				0.2094	0.3775	0.3703
PA-28RT	GA	Light Utility	Nominal	0.2753	0.4136	0.4494
Average values for low-wing single piston engine T-tail GA A/C →				0.2753	0.4136	0.4494
C310	GA	Light Utility	MTOW	0.4272	0.2497	0.5284
PA-30	GA	Light Utility	MTOW	0.2781	0.3274	0.4148
Average values for low-wing twin piston engine GA A/C →				0.3527	0.2886	0.4716
P2006T	GA	Light Utility	Heavy	0.2089	0.2993	0.3193
Average values for high-wing twin piston engine GA A/C →				0.2089	0.2993	0.3193

The design of General Aviation aircraft has attracted the attention of esteemed scholars, and some textbooks have been specifically written on the topic, with *General Aviation Aircraft Design* by Gudmundsson [13] being the most popular.

General Aviation category is defined as all civilian flying except scheduled passenger airline service. Bush planes, floatplanes, homebuilt & light utility airplanes are thus GA aircraft.

5.21 X-Plane

Table 5.43: Mass Properties Data of X-Planes

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
X-1	8410	Body	1981	9182	10519	N/A	25.9	28	31.00	[88]
X-2	12375	Body	5043	25474	29106	782	N/A	32.3	38.08	[37]
X-3	21900	Body	4100	61200	65100	4200	N/A	22.6875	66.75	
X-15	14318	Body	3600	85000	86500	-650	N/A	22.36	49.50	
X-24A	6362	Body	1544	8538	9346	40	N/A	19.16	37.50	[89]
X-24B	8500	Body	2650	23500	23850	660	64.0	19.0	37.50	[90]
X-29	14583	Body	4541	51746	56931	2559	-8.9	27.20	48.10	[91]
X-31	14500	Body	3090	34300	35200	-145	N/A	23.83	43.33	[92]
X-35B [†]	30979	Body	16581	92035	102594	-1688	N/A	33.00	51.18	[47]
	34428		17916	100365	112109	-2023				
X-43A	2823.3	Body	54.46	851.40	880.37	23.51	N/A	5.0	12.33	[93]

Note. †: X-35B is the prototype of 5th-generation fighter jet F-35B.

Table 5.44: Radii of Gyration for X-Planes

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
X-1	X-Plane	Rocket Plane	Nominal	0.1966	0.3824	0.4301
X-2		Rocket Plane	Empty	0.2242	0.4274	0.4944
X-3		Tech. Demo.	Heavy	0.2164	0.2841	0.4374
X-15		Hypersonic	Light	0.2544	0.5584	0.7761
X-24A		Lifting body	Light	0.2917	0.3505	0.4853
X-24B		Lifting body	Light	0.3334	0.5030	0.6727
X-29		Tech. Demo.	Nominal	0.2327	0.4443	0.5953
X-31		Fighter (TVC)	Nominal	0.2198	0.4027	0.5264
X-35B [†]		STOVL	Empty	0.2515	0.3821	0.4905
			Nominal	0.2480	0.3785	0.4864
X-43A		Hypersonic	Nominal	0.3151	0.5053	0.7311

Note. †: Use the radii of gyration for X-35B to estimate the MoI of a conceptual 5th-generation fighter jet.

The X-planes might be categorized under other titles accordingly, but since they are more generally known as the X-planes, they have been listed separately here. Also note that finding a grand average for X-planes is a vain endeavour, as they all represent different aircraft types. Use them to have more data on a specific A/C class, e.g., lifting bodies.

5.22 Delta-Wing

Table 5.45: Mass Properties Data of Delta-Wing Aircraft

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
F-16XL	28318	Body	22352	104027	123293	-559	45.0	32.40	54.16	[94]
X-31	14500	Body	3090	34300	35200	-145	N/A	23.83	43.33	[92]
XF-92A	15560	Body	6000	35000	38400	1°	25.5	31.33	42.80	[95,96]
YF-102	30394	Body	13200	106000	114600	3540	N/A	37.03	52.40	[37]
F-106B	29776	Body	18634	177858	191236	5539	30.5	38.13	70.87	[39]
FD2	12500	Body	6600	24800	33000	600	N/A	26.83	51.70	[97]
BAC 221	16000	Body	8410	49789	54246	1200	N/A	25.00	57.58	[97]
HP.115	5070	Body	1508	16142	17671	3.9°	N/A	20.51	50.33	[98]
Avro 707B	7376	Body	4247	15109	19720	N/A	N/A	43.00	50.92	[99]

Table 5.46: Radii of Gyration for Delta-Wing Aircraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
F-16XL	Fighter	Experimental	CrArrow	0.3111	0.4015	0.5469
Average values for Cranked-Arrow Delta-Wing Fighter A/C →				0.3111	0.4015	0.5469
X-31 [†]	X-Plane	Fighter (TVC)	Canard Delta	0.2198	0.4027	0.5264
Average values for Canard Delta Experimental Fighter A/C →				0.2198	0.4027	0.5264
XF-92A	Interceptor	Experimental	Tailless Delta	0.2249	0.3975	0.4808
YF-102	Interceptor	Prototype	Tailless Delta	0.2019	0.4043	0.4926
F-106B	Interceptor	Fighter	Tailless Delta	0.2354	0.3912	0.5275
Average values for U.S. Tailless Delta-Wing Interceptor A/C →				0.2207	0.3977	0.5003
FD2	SST R&D	Experimental	Tailless Delta	0.3072	0.3091	0.4694
BAC 221	SST R&D	Experimental	Ogival Delta	0.3290	0.3476	0.5059
HP.115	SST R&D	Experimental	Slender Delta	0.3017	0.4022	0.5979
Avro 707B	Bomber	Experimental	Tailless Delta	0.2002	0.3189	0.3950
Average values for British Experimental Delta-Wing A/C →				0.2845	0.3445	0.4921

Note. †: Use the data for X-31 to estimate the MoI of a canard delta fighter such as Eurofighter Typhoon and Dassault Rafale. Raymer was responsible for the early design of the Rockwell-MBB X-31. Final design of the X-31 aligns with the average nondimensional radii of gyration of modern fighter jets as given in Table 5.4.

Note: The designs of the B-58, Orbiter, and XB-70 also exhibit a delta-wing configuration. The data for these A/C and S/C have been previously provided elsewhere.

5.23 Flying Wing

Table 5.47: Mass Properties Data of Flying Wing

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
RB-49A	213500	Body	4.90E+6	4.65E+5	5.46E+6	N/A	N/A	172.0	53.0	[5]

Table 5.48: Radii of Gyration for Flying Wing

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
RB-49A	Flying Wing	Recon.	MTOW	0.3160	0.3160	0.5100
Average values for Flying Wing (B-49 type) →				0.3160	0.3160	0.5100

Note: For flying wings $I_{yy} < I_{xx}$ due to $L < b$, as in the case of sailplanes.

5.24 Other

Table 5.49: Mass Properties Data of Other Aircraft

A/C	US Units (W in lb; I in slug-ft ² ; CG in % MAC; b/L in ft)									Ref.
	W	Axes	I _{xx}	I _{yy}	I _{zz}	I _{xz} /ε	CG	b	L	
X-15	14318	Body	3600	85000	86500	-650	N/A	22.36	49.50	[37]
X-43A	2823.3	Body	54.46	851.40	880.37	23.51	N/A	5.00	12.33	[93]
D-558-II	10000	Body	2920	33300	26220	N/A	25	25.00	42.00	[100]

Table 5.50: Radii of Gyration for Other Aircraft

General Info				Radii of Gyration		
A/C	Class	Subclass	Config.	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
X-15	Hypersonic	Rocket Plane	Light	0.2544	0.5584	0.7761
X-43A	Hypersonic	Scramjet	Nominal	0.3151	0.5053	0.7311
D-558-II	Supersonic	Rocket Plane	Light	0.2452	0.4929	0.5483

Note: Other aircraft are those that cannot be fitted into other categories conveniently and hypersonic vehicle selections from X-planes.

The average nondimensional radii of gyration just given are also collectively presented in Table 5.51 in the order of appearance for ease of reference. The newly designed aircraft is most likely to fall into one of the categories given in Table 5.51.

Table 5.51: Summary of Average Nondimensional Radii of Gyration

Class	\bar{R}_x	\bar{R}_y	\bar{R}_z
Jet Fighter			
Generations 1 st to 3 rd	0.2300	0.3851	0.4938
Generations 4 th to 5 th	0.2313	0.3943	0.4933
Attack	0.2557	0.3769	0.4538
Jet Trainer	0.2831	0.3746	0.4963
Business Jet			
4 jet engines on rear fuselage	0.3264	0.3928	0.5081
4 piston engines under the wings	0.4279	0.2941	0.4876
2 jet engines on rear fuselage	0.5102	0.3263	0.5664
Supersonic Airliner	0.2555	0.3773	0.5402
Regional Airliner			
Twin piston-propeller driven	0.2267	0.3581	0.3789
Twin turboprop-driven	0.2934	0.3595	0.4480
Tiltwing VTOL	0.3379	0.3750	0.4796
Biplanes	0.2748	0.4073	0.4199
Lifting Body	0.4295	0.5076	0.6842
Reconnaissance (Mach 3+)	0.3632	0.4025	0.5818
Sailplane	0.3128	0.4108	0.5039
Observation	0.3280	0.3616	0.4778
Jet VTOL			
Experimental	0.2611	0.3421	0.4352
Attack	0.2372	0.3375	0.4320
Cargo	0.5107	0.3582	0.5795
Tiltrotor VTOL (XV-15 type)	0.6780	0.3134	0.6594
HPA		See Table 5.32	
Spacecraft (Orbiter)	0.3025	0.5347	0.6632
Airliner			
Twin turboprop short-haul	0.2720	0.2742	0.3813
Four jet-engined narrow-body	0.3154	0.3393	0.4676
Four jet-engined wide-body	0.2979	0.3565	0.4666
Bomber			
Twin piston-propeller driven	0.2849	0.3054	0.4110
Delta-wing 4 jet-engined	0.3384	0.3108	0.4497
Variable-sweep strategic	0.1584	0.3551	0.3913
Delta-wing supersonic bomber	0.2356	0.4252	0.5761
Cargo Plane			
Low-wing twin piston-propeller	0.1949	0.3510	0.3505
High-wing four jet engine	0.3373	0.3191	0.4502
High-wing twin turboprop engine	0.2722	0.3138	0.4044
High-wing four turboprop engine	0.3052	0.3411	0.4405
General Aviation			
Low-wing single piston engine	0.2098	0.4323	0.4229
High-wing single piston engine	0.2093	0.3205	0.3389
Floatplane (High-wing single engine)	0.2094	0.3775	0.3703
Low-wing single piston engine T-tail	0.2753	0.4136	0.4494
Low-wing twin piston engine	0.3527	0.2886	0.4716
High-wing twin piston engine	0.2089	0.2993	0.3193
X-Planes		See Table 5.44	
Delta-Wing			
Cranked-Arrow Fighter	0.3111	0.4015	0.5469
Canard Delta Fighter	0.2198	0.4027	0.5264
American Interceptor	0.2207	0.3977	0.5003
British Experimental	0.2845	0.3445	0.4921
Flying Wing (B-49 type)	0.3160	0.3160	0.5100
Other		See Table 5.50	

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Appendices

A Discussion: Mass or Weight?

By all means, mass is the total amount of matter contained in any type of three-dimensional body, whether it be an aircraft, spacecraft, or other aerial vehicle. The mass of an object is constant regardless of the reference frame, observer, or planet. Say, a spacecraft designed on Earth having a mass of 15000 kg preserves this property on the Moon and elsewhere.

Weight, on the other hand, is dependent on the local gravitational acceleration that acts at the center of mass of an object at any place, and is numerically calculated by $W = mg$. Physically speaking, weight is a force (force = mass \times acceleration, hence $\vec{W} = m\vec{g}$) that has a numeric quantity, and in SI units, it is denoted as either N or $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}/\text{s}^2$ or in US customary units lb_f or $\text{slug}\cdot\text{ft}/\text{s}^2$.

Traditionally, in aircraft design in US practice, weight is given in terms of lb (what is meant by lb is lb_m rather than lb_f) and mass in slug. This is the confusing part, since both lb and slug can be converted to kg, since they are both mass units. In order to prevent this confusion, the American practice is followed in this report: W is given in lb, and m is given in slug, which also means to say that when the “weight” of an aerial vehicle is mentioned, it is understood that lb_m is referred to, rather than lb_f . Whenever the mass of a vehicle is referred to, it is understood that the mass is given in slugs.

If SI units are to be used in an aircraft design project, to prevent confusion, the mass of the vehicle should still be called “mass” and the appropriate unit then is kg.

Another confusion might arise with the interchangeable use of the center of mass (CM) and center of gravity (CG). Physically speaking, the center of mass of any object is fixed in space and does not change with respect to a reference frame and gravitational acceleration. On the other hand, the center of gravity is affected by a nonuniform gravitational field. However, since conventional aircraft are operated in the Earth’s atmosphere, where the gravitational field is uniform, the CM and CG of an airplane are coincident.

Addendum: It is often required to convert the mass and inertia units from one system of units to another. For ease of reference, these conversions are given here:

- multiply kg by 2.20462262 to get lb_m
- multiply kg by 0.0685217656 to get slug
- multiply $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$ by 0.7375621419 to get $\text{slug}\cdot\text{ft}^2$
- multiply $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$ by 23.730360404 to get $\text{lb}\cdot\text{ft}^2$ ($\text{lb}\cdot\text{ft}^2$ is rarely used for aircraft MoI)

Reverse conversions are simply divisions, e.g., divide lb_m by 2.20462 to get kg, etc.

B Effect of Mass Properties on Dynamic Modes

Previously, it was mentioned that the mass properties also affect the dynamic modes. The effect of mass properties on dynamic modes can be studied in two ways: i) varying each mass property one by one while others are kept constant (this would be an unrealistic study, since W affects MoI & PoI), ii) varying W (and hence increasing the values of MoI and absolute value of PoI) and CG separately. In this study, the second approach is adopted because it provides universal trends applicable to conventional aircraft. The parameters under consideration are varied as follows: a 5% increase in weight and a 1% forward shift in the CG location in terms of MAC, which are investigated separately. In the ‘‘Trend’’ column, the percent change is omitted because it may differ for each aircraft; instead, the trends are indicated qualitatively using increase, no change, or decrease symbols. A change of less than 1% in the dynamic parameter is shown as no change. The aircraft used in this study is a conceptual fifth-generation fighter jet modeled and analyzed in ADA. The baseline weight for this study was 46798 lb. The MoI and PoI values used are: 71680, 193530, 268875, and -1502 slug-ft² for I_{xx} , I_{yy} , I_{zz} , and I_{xz} , respectively.

Table B.1: Effect of Mass Properties on Dynamic Modes of Aircraft

	Dynamic Parameter	Trend (\uparrow , \approx , \downarrow)	Parameter varied	Direction (\uparrow , fwd)
Longitudinal	$\omega_{n_{sp}}$	\approx \uparrow	$W (\Rightarrow I_{yy} \uparrow)$ CG	\uparrow fwd
	ζ_{sp}	\downarrow \downarrow	$W (\Rightarrow I_{yy} \uparrow)$ CG	\uparrow fwd
	$\omega_{n_{ph}}$	\uparrow \uparrow	$W (\Rightarrow I_{yy} \uparrow)$ CG	\uparrow fwd
	ζ_{ph}	\uparrow \uparrow	$W (\Rightarrow I_{yy} \uparrow)$ CG	\uparrow fwd
Lateral-Directional	$\omega_{n_{dr}}$	\downarrow \uparrow	$W (\Rightarrow I_{xx}, I_{zz}, I_{xz} \uparrow)$ CG	\uparrow fwd
	ζ_{dr}	\downarrow \downarrow	$W (\Rightarrow I_{xx}, I_{zz}, I_{xz} \uparrow)$ CG	\uparrow fwd
	τ_s	\downarrow \uparrow	$W (\Rightarrow I_{xx}, I_{zz}, I_{xz} \uparrow)$ CG	\uparrow fwd
	τ_r	\uparrow \approx	$W (\Rightarrow I_{xx}, I_{zz}, I_{xz} \uparrow)$ CG	\uparrow fwd

Note. The subscripts sp, ph, dr, s, and r denote short-period, phugoid, dutch roll, spiral, and roll modes, respectively.

Note: The trends presented herein are taken from ADA, which uses a linear aircraft model. These trends are obtained in the presence of conventional dynamic modes as cited in the table, i.e., in the absence of tuck or coupled roll-spiral modes.

C Transformation of Inertia

C.1 Method of Thelander

Per Thelander [1], who worked at Douglas Aircraft, the inertia transformations are carried out as follows. Note that $I_{yy} = I_{yy_s} = I_{yy_p}$ since y_b , y_s , and y_p axes are coincident.

Table C.1: Inertia Transformation from Stability to Body Axes (Thelander)

Body	Coefficients of Transform.			
	$\sin^2 \alpha$	$\cos^2 \alpha$	$\sin \alpha \cos \alpha$	1
I_{xx}	I_{zz_s}	I_{xx_s}	$2I_{xz_s}$	0
I_{yy}	0	0	0	I_{yy_s}
I_{zz}	I_{xx_s}	I_{zz_s}	$-2I_{xz_s}$	0
I_{xz}	$-I_{xz_s}$	I_{xz_s}	$I_{zz_s} - I_{xx_s}$	0

Table C.2: Inertia Transformation from Body to Stability Axes (Thelander)

Stab.	Coefficients of Transform.			
	$\sin^2 \alpha$	$\cos^2 \alpha$	$\sin \alpha \cos \alpha$	1
I_{xx_s}	I_{zz}	I_{xx}	$-2I_{xz}$	0
I_{yy_s}	0	0	0	I_{yy}
I_{zz_s}	I_{xx}	I_{zz}	$2I_{xz}$	0
I_{xz_s}	$-I_{xz}$	I_{xz}	$I_{xx} - I_{zz}$	0

Table C.3: Inertia Transformation from Principal to Body Axes (Thelander)

Body	Coefficients of Transform.			
	$\sin^2 \epsilon$	$\cos^2 \epsilon$	$\sin \epsilon \cos \epsilon$	1
I_{xx}	I_{zz_p}	I_{xx_p}	0	0
I_{yy}	0	0	0	I_{yy_p}
I_{zz}	I_{xx_p}	I_{zz_p}	0	0
I_{xz}	0	0	$I_{zz_p} - I_{xx_p}$	0

Table C.4: Inertia Transformation from Body to Principal Axes (Thelander)

Prin.	Coefficients of Transform.			
	$\sin^2 \epsilon$	$\cos^2 \epsilon$	$\sin \epsilon \cos \epsilon$	1
I_{xx_p}	I_{zz}	I_{xx}	$-2I_{xz}$	0
I_{yy_p}	0	0	0	I_{yy}
I_{zz_p}	I_{xx}	I_{zz}	$2I_{xz}$	0
I_{xz_p}	$-I_{xz}$	I_{xz}	$I_{xx} - I_{zz}$	0

Table C.5: Inertia Transformation from Principal to Stability Axes (Thelander)

Stab.	Coefficients of Transform.			
	$\sin^2 \eta$	$\cos^2 \eta$	$\sin \eta \cos \eta$	1
I_{xx_s}	I_{zz_p}	I_{xx_p}	0	0
I_{yy_s}	0	0	0	I_{yy_p}
I_{zz_s}	I_{xx_p}	I_{zz_p}	0	0
I_{xz_s}	0	0	$I_{xx_p} - I_{zz_p}$	0

Table C.6: Inertia Transformation from Stability to Principal Axes (Thelander)

Prin.	Coefficients of Transform.			
	$\sin^2 \eta$	$\cos^2 \eta$	$\sin \eta \cos \eta$	1
I_{xx_p}	I_{zz_s}	I_{xx_s}	$2I_{xz_s}$	0
I_{yy_p}	0	0	0	I_{yy_s}
I_{zz_p}	I_{xx_s}	I_{zz_s}	$-2I_{xz_s}$	0
I_{xz_p}	$-I_{xz_s}$	I_{xz_s}	$I_{zz_s} - I_{xx_s}$	0

C.2 Method of Wolowicz

Per Wolowicz [101], who worked at NASA, the inertia transformations are carried out as follows. Note that $I_{yy} = I_{yy_s} = I_{yy_p}$ since y_b , y_s , and y_p axes are coincident.

Table C.7: Inertia Transformation from Stability to Body Axes (Wolowicz)

Body	Coefficients of Transformation from Stability to Body Axes		
	$\sin 2\alpha$	$\cos 2\alpha$	1
I_{xx}	I_{xz_s}	$-(I_{zz_s} - I_{xx_s})/2$	$(I_{xx_s} + I_{zz_s})/2$
I_{yy}	0	0	I_{yy_s}
I_{zz}	$-I_{xz_s}$	$(I_{zz_s} - I_{xx_s})/2$	$(I_{zz_s} + I_{xx_s})/2$
I_{xz}	$-(I_{xx_s} - I_{zz_s})/2$	I_{xz_s}	0

Table C.8: Inertia Transformation from Body to Stability Axes (Wolowicz)

Stab.	Coefficients of Transformation from Body to Stability Axes		
	$\sin 2\alpha$	$\cos 2\alpha$	1
I_{xx_s}	$-I_{xz}$	$-(I_{zz} - I_{xx})/2$	$(I_{xx} + I_{zz})/2$
I_{yy_s}	0	0	I_{yy}
I_{zz_s}	I_{xz}	$(I_{zz} - I_{xx})/2$	$(I_{zz} + I_{xx})/2$
I_{xz_s}	$(I_{xx} - I_{zz})/2$	I_{xz}	0

Table C.9: Inertia Transformation from Principal to Body Axes (Wolowicz)

Body	Coefficients of Transformation from Principal to Body Axes		
	$\sin 2\epsilon$	$\cos 2\epsilon$	1
I_{xx}	0	$-(I_{zz_p} - I_{xx_p})/2$	$(I_{xx_p} + I_{zz_p})/2$
I_{yy}	0	0	I_{yy_p}
I_{zz}	0	$(I_{zz_p} - I_{xx_p})/2$	$(I_{zz_p} + I_{xx_p})/2$
I_{xz}	$-(I_{xx_p} - I_{zz_p})/2$	0	0

John A. Thelander (1925-2018) was a distinguished naval aviator, aeronautical engineer, and authority in the study of wake turbulence. At the age of seventeen, he enlisted in the United States Navy during the Second World War. Following the conclusion of the war, he pursued higher education, obtaining a BA in Aeronautical Engineering from Purdue University, followed by a master's degree from Stanford University. He subsequently joined Douglas Aircraft Company in Long Beach, CA, where he conducted seminal research on wake turbulence phenomena. He was also a licensed civilian pilot.

Table C.10: Inertia Transformation from Body to Principal Axes (Wolowicz)

Prin.	Coefficients of Transformation from Body to Principal Axes		
	$\sin 2\epsilon$	$\cos 2\epsilon$	1
I_{xx_p}	$-I_{xz}$	$-(I_{zz} - I_{xx})/2$	$(I_{xx} + I_{zz})/2$
I_{yy_p}	0	0	I_{yy}
I_{zz_p}	I_{xz}	$(I_{zz} - I_{xx})/2$	$(I_{zz} + I_{xx})/2$
I_{xz_p}	0	0	0

Table C.11: Inertia Transformation from Principal to Stability Axes (Wolowicz)

Stab.	Coefficients of Transformation from Principal to Stability Axes		
	$\sin 2\eta$	$\cos 2\eta$	1
I_{xx_s}	0	$-(I_{zz_p} - I_{xx_p})/2$	$(I_{xx_p} + I_{zz_p})/2$
I_{yy_s}	0	0	I_{yy_p}
I_{zz_s}	0	$(I_{zz_p} - I_{xx_p})/2$	$(I_{zz_p} + I_{xx_p})/2$
I_{xz_s}	$(I_{xx_p} - I_{zz_p})/2$	0	0

Table C.12: Inertia Transformation from Stability to Principal Axes (Wolowicz)

Prin.	Coefficients of Transformation from Stability to Principal Axes		
	$\sin 2\eta$	$\cos 2\eta$	1
I_{xx_p}	I_{xz_s}	$-(I_{zz_s} - I_{xx_s})/2$	$(I_{xx_s} + I_{zz_s})/2$
I_{yy_p}	0	0	I_{yy_s}
I_{zz_p}	$-I_{xz_s}$	$(I_{zz_s} - I_{xx_s})/2$	$(I_{zz_s} + I_{xx_s})/2$
I_{xz_p}	0	0	0

The mathematical equivalence of the methods proposed by Thelander and Wolowicz are to be proved in Appendix C.3.

Chester H. Wolowicz (1914–1992) was a research engineer at NASA’s Dryden Flight Research Center (formerly the NACA High-Speed Flight Station) in Edwards, California. He authored and co-authored numerous NACA/NASA technical reports on stability and control, aerodynamic modeling, flight-test and wind-tunnel correlation, and similitude and scaling for model testing. Wolowicz made significant contributions to the understanding of longitudinal and lateral-directional stability characteristics of both experimental and production aircraft. He played a key role in research programs involving high-performance and supersonic aircraft, including detailed studies of the X-15 and XB-70.

C.3 Comparison of Methods of Thelander and Wolowicz

In order to show the mathematical equivalence of the methods proposed by Thelander and Wolowicz, the transformation of inertia from body to stability axes is investigated.

Thelander: $f(\alpha) = I_{xx_s} = I_{zz} \sin^2 \alpha + I_{xx} \cos^2 \alpha - 2I_{xz} \sin \alpha \cos \alpha$

Wolowicz: $g(\alpha) = I_{xx_s} = -I_{xz} \sin 2\alpha - \cos 2\alpha(I_{zz} - I_{xx})/2 + (I_{xx} + I_{zz})/2$

Proof. It will be shown that both expressions are equal, i.e., $f(\alpha) = g(\alpha)$.

Remember the trigonometric identities:

$$\sin^2 \alpha = \frac{1 - \cos 2\alpha}{2}$$

$$\cos^2 \alpha = \frac{1 + \cos 2\alpha}{2}$$

$$\sin \alpha \cos \alpha = \frac{1}{2} \sin 2\alpha$$

Substituting those identities into $f(\alpha)$:

$$f(\alpha) = \frac{I_{zz}(1 - \cos 2\alpha)}{2} + \frac{I_{xx}(1 + \cos 2\alpha)}{2} - I_{xz} \sin 2\alpha$$

Distributing the trigonometric functions:

$$f(\alpha) = \frac{I_{xx} + I_{zz}}{2} + \frac{I_{xx} - I_{zz}}{2} \cos 2\alpha - I_{xz} \sin 2\alpha$$

Rearranging:

$$f(\alpha) = -I_{xz} \sin 2\alpha - \cos 2\alpha(I_{zz} - I_{xx})/2 + (I_{xx} + I_{zz})/2$$

Therefore:

$$f(\alpha) = g(\alpha)$$

i.e., both methods are mathematically equal. □

C.4 Derivation of Inertia Transformations

Previously in Section 1.2, it was discussed that the inertia is a tensor and is axis-dependent, and the transformation of inertia between body-fixed axes was given as proposed by Thelander and Wolowicz, which are mathematically the same formulations.

Since the tensors \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{I}_s , and \mathbf{I}_p represent the same physical properties in different Cartesian coordinate systems, they are all related by a similarity transformation as:

$$\mathbf{I}' = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{I}\mathbf{T}^{-1} \quad (\text{also implies that } \mathbf{I} = \mathbf{T}^{-1}\mathbf{I}'\mathbf{T}) \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where \mathbf{I}' represents the inertia tensor in the transformed axes, and the transformation matrix \mathbf{T} is:

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & \sin \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

representing a rotation about the y-axis, since all body-fixed axes can be transformed within themselves by a rotation about the y-axis, and angle θ is one of $\{\alpha, -\alpha, \epsilon, -\epsilon, \eta, -\eta\}$. Since \mathbf{I}' and \mathbf{I} are similar matrices, they have the same rank, trace, determinant, and eigenvalues. Also, matrix \mathbf{T} is orthogonal, i.e., $\mathbf{T}^{-1} = \mathbf{T}^T$. Hence, Equation C.1 can be written as:

$$\boxed{\mathbf{I}' = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{I}\mathbf{T}^T} \quad (\text{also implies that } \mathbf{I} = \mathbf{T}^T\mathbf{I}'\mathbf{T}) \quad (\text{C.3})$$

For instance, to transform the inertia tensor from body to principal axes ($\theta = -\epsilon$):

$$\mathbf{I}_p = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \epsilon & 0 & -\sin \epsilon \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \epsilon & 0 & \cos \epsilon \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx} & -I_{xy} & -I_{xz} \\ -I_{xy} & I_{yy} & -I_{yz} \\ -I_{xz} & -I_{yz} & I_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \epsilon & 0 & \sin \epsilon \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \epsilon & 0 & \cos \epsilon \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C.4})$$

Similarly, one can transform the stability axes inertia to body axes as ($\theta = \alpha$ in this case):

$$\mathbf{I} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha & 0 & \sin \alpha \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & 0 & \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx_s} & -I_{xy_s} & -I_{xz_s} \\ -I_{xy_s} & I_{yy_s} & -I_{yz_s} \\ -I_{xz_s} & -I_{yz_s} & I_{zz_s} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha & 0 & -\sin \alpha \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \alpha & 0 & \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

This implies that all body-axes inertia tensors can be transformed to another body-fixed axes by using Equation C.3, which will also yield relations for the transformation of I_{xy} and I_{yz} , which are missing in the methods of Thelander and Wolowicz for practical reasons.

D Weight and Balance Glossary

All Up Weight (AUW) The total weight of an aircraft and all of its contents at a specific time, also known as gross weight.

Arm The distance from the reference datum to the center of gravity of an item.

Ballast Additional fixed weights which can be removed, if necessary, that are carried, to ensure the center of gravity remains within the safe limits, in certain circumstances.

Butt Line A line through the symmetrical center of an aircraft from nose to tail. It serves as the datum for measuring the arms used to determine the lateral CG. This is almost the same as wing stations, except butt lines are used to address locations in the fuselage (sometimes, they are also used to address locations in the wing and horizontal stabilizer).

Center of Gravity (CG) The point at which the aircraft would balance if suspended.

Center of Gravity Envelope A plot of center of gravity vs. gross weight for various loading conditions. Established CG limits are normally included on the plot.

Center of Gravity Limits Extremes of movement which the CG can have without making the aircraft unsafe to fly.

Crew Weight The weight of the occupants required to operate the aircraft.

Empty Weight or Standard Empty Weight, the weight of the aircraft excluding usable fuel, crew, and traffic load but including fixed ballast, engine oil, engine coolants (if applicable), and all hydraulic fluid and all other fluids required for normal operation and aircraft systems.

Fuel Weight The weight of the fuel required to complete the design mission.

Gross Weight Total weight of the aircraft for a specific operating condition.

Growth Factor Pounds of gross weight that must be added to a vehicle per pound of fixed empty weight to maintain a given performance level. Its formal definition is given as: $GF = 1 / (1 - (W_e/W_0 + W_f/W_0))$. See Ref. [102] for more information.

Landing Weight The gross weight of the airplane, including all of its contents, at the time of landing.

Limit Load Factor A flight load factor with no factor of safety applied.

Maximum Ramp Weight The maximum weight at which an aircraft may commence taxiing, and it is equal to the maximum take-off weight plus taxi fuel and run-up fuel. It must not exceed the surface load-bearing strength.

Mean Aerodynamic Chord The chord which passes through the centroid of an aerodynamic surface. MAC of the wing is a primary reference for longitudinal CG locations. Center of gravity limits for fixed-wing aircraft (not rotorcraft) are usually expressed in terms of % MAC (% of distance from the leading edge to the trailing edge of the MAC).

Mission Profile A description of the aircraft mission, including take off, climb to altitude, cruise, combat, loiter, landing, etc.

Moment The product of the weight of an item multiplied by its arm.

Moment of Inertia That property of a body that requires an equivalent force moment application to achieve rotation about a given axis. Dependent not only on the mass of the body but also on its distribution. Equivalent to the summation of the product of the mass of each particle and the square of its radial distance from the rotational axis.

Payload The weight of passengers, cargo, and anything else carried by the aircraft.

Reference Datum Reference datum is an imaginary vertical plane from which all horizontal distances are measured for balance purposes.

Station A location along the airplane fuselage usually given in terms of distance (usually in inches) from the reference datum.

Tipback On the ground tipping of an aircraft to a tail down position.

Ultimate Load Factor A flight load factor with a factor of safety applied, usually a multiplier of 1.5 for manned flight vehicles.

Unusable Fuel That part of the fuel carried which is impossible to use because of the shape or position of particular tanks.

Unusable Oil That part of the oil lubrication system that cannot be removed due to the construction of the system.

Useful Load The difference between the design gross weight and the empty weight.

Water Line A vertical reference designation measured parallel to the ground, usually in inches. Location of the base line (WL0) might vary for any other aircraft.